

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

Protocol 4

EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Glocal Sites

(Final protocol)

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations in D3.2

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research and Innovation
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
YC	Youth Citizens
QH Cultural Hub	Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE CH	EPIC-WE Cultural Hub
EPIC-WE CGJ	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem	EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

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1. Introduction

The EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Glocal Sites is a comprehensive guide designed to facilitate the planning, execution, and evaluation of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs). These events merge game design with cultural heritage, European values, and youth participation to foster innovative, inclusive, and meaningful cultural interventions. Rooted in co-creation and participatory design principles, the protocol offers structured approaches for cultural institutions, creative industries partners, higher education institutions, and youth citizens to collaborate in creating culturally rich and socially relevant game experiences.

This document provides a framework integrating interdisciplinary research, theoretical perspectives, and practical guidelines for implementing CGJs at local and “glocal” levels. It shares lessons learned from the first two rounds of hub-organised EPIC-WE Local CGJs. It offers guiding principles for designing, executing and evaluating the CGJs based on these insights. The CGJ interventions aim to empower young participants by engaging them in the cultural production of game-making, ensuring their voices and creative contributions are central to the game development process. The protocol fosters transdisciplinary innovation within cultural game-making for youth empowerment by leveraging the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem.

How to Use This Document

This protocol is designed as both a theoretical and practical guide for implementing CGJs. Within this document, CGJs are divided into four key phases, each providing detailed guidance, lessons learned, and guiding principles for execution:

- **Cultural Game Jam Context:** This section establishes the foundation for a CGJ, defining its purpose, considering cultural heritage integration, and framing the problem space. It also outlines the importance of defining the roles and responsibilities of different partners involved in shaping the event.
- **Cultural Game Jam Design:** This phase focuses on structuring the CGJ, detailing the game jam format, participant recruitment strategies, logistics, and inclusive facilitation practices. It also includes guiding principles to ensure a well-supported, impactful event.
- **Cultural Game Jam Intervention:** This is the execution phase of the CGJ, during which participants engage in game-making within structured facilitation environments. This section provides strategies for team formation, mentorship, technical support, and real-time prototyping.

- **Cultural Game Jam Evaluation:** This phase outlines methodologies for assessing the success of CGJs in both local and global contexts, including jam-specific and long-term perspectives.

Each phase incorporates guiding principles, roles and responsibilities for different partners, and lessons learned from previous implementations. Additionally, the appendices include practical examples to support hands-on application.

By taking guidance and inspiration from these structured guidelines, CHs can adapt CGJs to their specific contexts, ensuring impactful and sustainable cultural interventions.

Key Topics Covered

The document is structured to provide a stage-like approach to designing and executing a CGJ, including theoretical insights, methodological considerations, and practical applications. Key topics include:

1. **Theory and Concepts:** This section introduces foundational frameworks, including the Quadruple Helix Innovation Model, Living Labs, QH Cultural Hubs, and principles from Inclusive, Pluriversal, and Transversal Design that guide the development of CGJs and ensure they evolve into culturally inclusive and participatory experiences.
2. **Methodology:** EPIC-WE CGJs employ a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach, integrating iterative design, empirical evaluation, and stakeholder engagement. The methodology section outlines a structured process for problem identification, co-design, intervention implementation, and evaluation to ensure the effectiveness and adaptability of CGJs.
3. **Youth Empowerment:** A core focus of the EPIC-WE CGJs is engaging and empowering youth participants, which is also implemented by developing the Youth Advisory Boards (YAB) in the co-creative process of intervention development. This section emphasises the role of youth in shaping game narratives, fostering agency, and enabling meaningful participation in cultural discourse through game-making.
4. **Inclusion and Accessibility:** Recognising participants' diverse backgrounds and needs, the protocol details strategies for creating inclusive and enabling spaces. This includes considerations for accessibility, diverse representation in cultural narratives, and fostering an environment of equity and participation.
5. **Cultural Game Jam Context:** The protocol guides identifying a CGJ's problem space, including its key aims.

6. **Cultural Game Jam Design:** This section details the structure of events, the format of the game jam, logistics, and recruitment strategies. It provides insights into planning and execution while incorporating inclusivity considerations and engagement techniques.
7. **Cultural Game Jam Intervention:** Practical guidelines for conducting the on-site CGJ interventions, including team formation, mentorship structures, logistical coordination, and real-time facilitation. The document also emphasises flexibility, iterative prototyping, and fostering creativity in a collaborative setting.
8. **Evaluation & Impact Measurement:** The protocol shares insights for evaluating CGJs to ensure continuous improvement and scalability.
9. **Future Directions and Sustainability:** Future research on CGJs should enhance inclusivity, sustainability, and impact. Key recommendations include integrating youth participation in advisory roles, emphasising inclusive design, and fostering cross-sector collaborations through the QHE. Additionally, research should evaluate local versus global approaches and refine materials, tools, and stakeholder engagement strategies.

Conclusion

This protocol is an inspirational guide that offers practical support for designing, planning, executing, and evaluating CGJs. It provides lessons learned, guiding principles, and suggestions for distributing roles and responsibilities. However, it is not a rigid blueprint but rather a flexible framework that can be adapted to different contexts and needs. The specific configuration of partners, the jam's location, and the expertise and aspirations of the organising team will ultimately shape each CGJ's implementation.

This document encourages QH Cultural Hubs to explore new possibilities and adapt practices to best suit their participants and local environments. It fosters co-creation, inclusivity, and cultural engagement and is intended to be a living resource that evolves alongside the growing field of cultural game-making, inspiring continuous innovation and meaningful cultural participation through games.

2. Theory & Concepts

2.1 Quadruple Helix Innovation

In EPIC-WE, the collaborative and co-creative foundation - epistemically and practically - comes from the Quadruple Helix (QH) innovation system that expands the traditional Triple Helix model by incorporating a fourth helix: the public, specifically defined as the culture- and media-based public and civil society. Conceived by Carayannis and Campbell (2006) and refined in subsequent works (2009, 2012, 2022), the QH integrates government, industry, academia, and citizens as equal partners in innovation processes. While the government encompasses public authorities and policymakers, the industry includes businesses and networks, and academia involves universities and research bodies; the fourth helix—citizens—distinguishes the QH by emphasising their active participation in co-creating innovations. This inclusion extends to communities, organisations, and networks that influence or benefit from these innovations, focusing strongly on cultural domains such as art, media, heritage, and values. By centring on citizens as both contributors and end-users, as empowered participants and partners, the QH positions culture as a critical component of knowledge and innovation, shifting the focus from knowledge economies to knowledge democracies. The later section on 'Youth Empowerment' details the empowerment and integration of (youth) citizens.

QH ecosystems are designed to foster collective creativity and collaboration through Mode 3 knowledge production, which combines and integrates diverse paradigms across disciplines, sectors, and other cultural and societal boundaries (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012). This approach foregrounds cultural and social innovation, enabling intricate, multi-directional interactions between partners and promoting democracy as a driver of innovation. Studies such as those by Taratori et al. (2021) and Schütz et al. (2019) highlight that public participation, partner cooperation, and long-term commitment are key to the success of QH ecosystems. Projects like EPIC-WE exemplify this model, enabling and creating spaces for cross-sector co-creation in cultural innovation by bringing together higher education, cultural institutions, creative industries, and youth citizens. These "meetings in the middle" signify the QH's capacity to catalyse structural transformation and shared cultural futures, addressing real-world needs through equitable, participatory innovation.

2.2 Living Labs and QH Cultural Hubs

Living Labs (LLs) are approached in EPIC-WE as a concept and practice to materialise and enact the co-creative and innovative quadruple helix framework, leading to the Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hubs (hereafter *QH Cultural Hubs*; the QH Cultural Hub are defined and elaborated in D3.2: Protocol 1 and D3.3). LLs represent a unique approach to research and innovation, serving as both a methodology and a real-world environment for participatory co-creation. Originating from W.J. Mitchell's PlaceLab (2004), LLs are deeply influenced by Scandinavian participatory design traditions that emphasise collaboration, cultural values, and human-centred approaches (Fuglsang et al., 2021; Steen & van Bueren, 2017). These environments, ranging from specific rooms to entire cities, prioritise co-creation with citizens, fostering democratic participation and emphasising cultural and social impacts over purely technical solutions. LLs integrate diverse methods, including ethnographic research, human-centred design, and democratic innovation, to create iterative, real-world feedback loops that enhance sustainability and user engagement. As open innovation ecosystems, LLs unite citizens, researchers, companies, and government agencies as intermediaries to co-create solutions with lasting societal value.

By positioning innovation in real-life contexts, LLs enable transdisciplinary collaboration and cross-sector partnerships that transcend conventional boundaries of knowledge and practice (see, e.g., Protocol 1, D3.2; Protocol 1, D3.1). They serve as "third spaces" where participants from various sectors can "de-centre" existing ways of working and "centre" new, transformative modes of collaboration. LLs test and develop innovations and facilitate empowered participation by integrating citizens as co-researchers and co-creators. This participatory focus is refined through tailored typologies—research-driven, industry-driven, community-driven, or testbed-driven LLs—each adapted to specific goals and outcomes. In EPIC-WE, Cultural Living Labs (CLLs) are conceptualised as meso-level environments that animate macro-level quadruple helix ecosystems and foster cultural innovation— and they are defined and named as QH Cultural Hubs. Through practices like game-making and culture-making, these CLLs exemplify the LL ethos by co-creating meaningful societal impact, emphasising collaboration, and transforming theoretical innovation systems into practical, citizen-focused realities, as materialised and exemplified by CGJs.

2.3 Inclusive, Pluriversal, and Transversal Design

This protocol further draws from theories and practices of inclusive (ID), pluriversal (PD), and transversal design (TD). ID is a human-centred approach to creating products and services accessible to and usable by the broadest possible range of people

without requiring specialised adaptations to develop and provide strategies and methods for those normally not designed for (Collier, 2020). It emphasises understanding user diversity and acknowledging that individuals vary in their capabilities, needs, and aspirations. By focusing on edge users—those with unique needs—ID fosters innovation and creativity, delivering solutions that benefit these users and a much broader audience. This approach critiques one-size-fits-all solutions, advocating for flexible and adaptable systems that honour individual self-determination while accommodating diverse experiences. This is associated with PD approaches that seek to integrate a range of locally rooted perspectives and a more complex view of the overarching values and purposes of design for bringing about ways of being—individual, group, or cultural—despite contradictions and conflicts in different contexts and narratives at a micro-scale.

The multiplicity of worlds and perspectives in a pluriversal approach (Escobar, 2017) seeks to balance the power inequalities of the privileged and oppressed. One way to diminish and address power inequities is to enable radical and epistemic participation towards designing *with and through* the people for whom the impact of the design is the greatest: in EPIC-WE, the youth citizens. A pluriversal perspective challenges the traditional view of design as a transactional practice, instead focusing on *relationality*, emphasising the diversity and complexity of other perspectives. A focus on *relationality* values trust-building, long-term commitments, and dedication to understanding partners, participants, and their future prosperity. It is a matter of collaborative care that considers tension, hesitation, and power dynamics (Scheel et al., 2019). Moreover, and to extend the pluriversal elements, we further draw inspiration from TD, wherein the “transversal “we” is not a totalising, undifferentiated shared identity or fragmented collection of different irreconcilable parts” (Hsu, 2021). As Hsu (2021) further argues:

“Designing conditions that nurture potential for the rupture of radical creativity; where tensions in and through a plurality of perspectives generatively lead to transversal encounters of glimpsing “wholeness”: creative moments of encounter where “us” and “them” might co-create an emergent “we”.”

Viewing EPIC-WE as a potential - epistemically and practically - to nurture an emergent we of radical creativity, an *epic we*, through difference and similarity, is of vital interest to the practical planning and implementations of CGJs. Towards moments of empowerment and wholeness - of new modes of creative and playful relationality and care (Holflod, 2024). By approaching and embedding inclusive, pluriversal, and transversal thinking and approaches into QH and LL practices, innovation ecosystems can deliver sustainable, equitable, and user-centred CGJs that reflect and respond to the diversity and multiplicity of their stakeholders.

2.4 Cultural Game Jams

EPIC-WE innovates, tests, and refines a novel game-making format, Cultural Game Jams (CGJs), that integrates the principles of traditional game jams—short time frames, creative constraints, and public dissemination of game prototypes—with a focus on culture and cultural heritage. While game jams are celebrated for fostering creativity, innovation, and social connections, CGJs emphasise culturally explorative and value-sensitive game design that promotes diversity, inclusivity, and empowered participation. Building on transdisciplinary collaboration—both local and glocal (thus national and transnational) (Holflod et al., 2024; Nørgård & Holflod, 2024a), CGJs involve cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth participants (aged 16-25) to co-create games within and through cultural heritage settings. This approach highlights the potential of games as cultural artefacts and addresses the need for more diverse and sustainable practices in the global game industry. Implemented across three European sites—Óbidos (Portugal), Hilversum (The Netherlands), and Aarhus (Denmark)—as part of the EPIC-WE project, CGJs prioritise youth-empowered cultural participation and fostering communal, collaborative experiences that resonate with individual and social values in game-making and culture.

2.5 Sustainable Development Goals

The EPIC-WE project actively addresses and integrates the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into its developments and practical framework, ensuring its activities and interventions contribute to global priorities such as quality education, gender equality, economic growth, and sustainable communities. By creating games that foster learning and participation in an accessible and engaging format, with and across educational partners and participants, the project addresses SDG 4: Quality Education. These games promote sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, freedom, and European values generally while equipping youth with media literacy, entrepreneurial experiences, and social opportunities that complement formal education. Through both the development and playing of these games, EPIC-WE contributes to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities to enable and empower youth participants with experiences needed in the future.

In alignment with SDG 5: Gender Equality, the project addresses the systemic alienation of female and non-binary youth in the gaming sector by proposing strategies

and policies to combat discrimination and through inspiration from ID and PD, as described above. This effort seeks to foster inclusivity in game-making environments and open pathways for underrepresented groups to pursue careers in the creative industries. Additionally, EPIC-WE advances SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth by providing youth—particularly those from diverse and disengaged backgrounds—with interdisciplinary, transferable experiences through game-making in cultural contexts. This focus on creativity and collaboration enables participants to explore career opportunities in the game sector, cultural heritage institutions, and broader creative industries. The project lastly emphasises SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, particularly goal 11.4 on cultural heritage protection. By integrating cultural heritage into the creative value chains of the gaming and broader creative industries, EPIC-WE demonstrates its economic potential and fosters its preservation for future generations. The project strengthens advocacy for sustainable funding for cultural heritage institutions through creative reuse and active engagement, encouraging collaboration across diverse and complex sectors and working to ensure that cultural heritage remains a vital and sustainable component of modern societies.

3. Methodology

EPIC-WE is a design-based research and innovation project where CGJs are design interventions which are designed, evaluated, and iterated in—and across—the QH Cultural Hubs. To strengthen alignment between the project's methodological foundations and this protocol's structure, the practical dimensions of designing, intervening, and iterating CGJs follow the design-based frameworks of the project. However, it is extended and adapted to suit the specific cases of CGJs. The systematic literature reviews and best practice reports of WP2 (Costa et al., 2024a, 2024b) highlight that the applied game jam framework (Reid et al., 2020) is particularly interesting to EPIC-WE. The framework utilises four distinct phases, acting as a framework and guide to develop, deliver, and evaluate game jams. These phases relate meaningfully with the design-based phases, and the present practical protocol is thus structured as a synthesis of design-based research as a methodology and the applied game jam framework to support and strengthen dissemination and application of how to deliver CGJs.

EPIC-WE is an ambitious Design-Based Research and Innovation (DBR) project grounded in McKenney & Reeves's (2019) framework. It focuses on collaborative stakeholder efforts to design, implement, and evaluate CGJs. EPIC-WE's design-based process consists of three iterative phases. The Analysis and Exploration phase establishes the foundation by leveraging partner expertise and conducting a systematic literature review to understand key domains such as the quadruple helix context, games, game jams, and empowered participation. This phase supported the first round of interventions (local focus) and transitioned into exploring results from there towards redesigns of design interventions in the second round (global focus). The Design and Construction phase applies insights from the first phase to develop and document initial interventions, ecosystems, methods, and tools that foster collaboration between cultural heritage institutions (CHI), creative industries (CI), higher education institutions (HEI), and youth. It emphasises co-design with stakeholders, integrating state-of-the-art knowledge and best practices, and culminates in constructing practical solutions like CGJs for testing and evaluation. Finally, the Evaluation and Reflection phase tests the interventions through iterative evaluation of 12 CGJs, locally and then across the three European sites, to examine their soundness, feasibility, and impact. Results are analysed and integrated into subsequent research cycles, with reflection focusing on refining interventions and creating design resources. This iterative DBR approach ensures that EPIC-WE delivers well-grounded, impactful innovations that support cultural participation and youth empowerment. Consequently, DBR—generally and specifically—highlights the collaborative and iterative research and innovation processes of contextual inquiry, design of solutions, testing and interventions, and evaluations. In the context of this Practical Protocol, insights for iteration were drawn from analysis of the first two rounds of hub-organised EPIC-WE

Local CGJs, with the data collection, case study development and analysis of T4.3 and the evaluation data collected from T3.4 Focus Group Workshops serving as input for this document. Furthermore, the protocol draws from several empirical studies of the first round of CGJ interventions that address the CGJ format (Eriksson et al., 2025; Luz et al., 2024), experiences with initial designs of CGJs (Eriksson et al., 2024a, 2024b), how cultural and social learning and cultural participation is framed and experienced herein (Gonçalves et al., 2024; Holflod & Nørgård, 2024a; Holflod et al., 2024), how the quadruple helix innovation ecosystems operate in cultural domains (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024a), and the previous protocols from the initial rounds of the project (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024b, 2024c; Somers Miles et al., 2024),

The “Theoretical Framework for Game Jams in Applied Contexts” (Reid et al., 2020) outlines four key phases for designing and evaluating applied game jams. The first phase, Problem Space, establishes the purpose of the game jam by identifying the issue or outcome to be addressed and defining explicit design constraints to guide planning and evaluation. The second phase, Cultural Game Jam Design, structures the event to effectively address the Problem Space, focusing on two key aspects: Guiding Criteria, such as themes or scenarios to direct game development, and Logistics, which manage practical considerations like duration, resources, and participant expectations to ensure a well-supported and realistic environment. The third phase, Jam Delivery and Outcomes, involves the execution and management of the game jam. This phase evaluates success through the alignment of the games and participant experiences with the goals of the Problem Space, alongside learning outcomes for participants and insights gained by stakeholders. The final phase, Follow-on Opportunity, explores post-event possibilities such as continued project development, securing funding, fostering partnerships, and disseminating results. Together, these phases provide a comprehensive framework for creating impactful game jams that address real-world challenges, foster collaboration, and enable sustained innovation.

This protocol combines design-based research and innovation with the ‘Theoretical Framework for Game Jams in Applied Contexts’ to guide the design, delivery, and evaluation of CGJs. It is structured into four key phases:

1. Cultural Game Jam Context

Through analysis and exploration, collaboratively define the CGJ’s purpose, objectives, and constraints—its problem space. Drawing on literature reviews, partner expertise, and context-sensitive and cross-sector knowledge and experience, this phase identifies the specific challenges to address. It sets clear criteria and problems to align the jam with cultural and societal goals.

2. Cultural Game Jam Design

Co-creative design and construction of the CGJ to address the identified problem(s). Key elements include Guiding Criteria (themes or scenarios to direct development) and Logistics (practical planning for time, resources, and participant expectations). Co-creation with stakeholders is vital to ensure practical, well-supported solutions for implementation and practical feasibility.

3. Cultural Game Jam Intervention

This phase involves executing and iteratively testing game jams, focusing on maintaining alignment with the defined objectives, ensuring participant engagement, and supporting the interplay of games, citizenship, values, and cultural heritage. Delivery can vary from open-ended, participant-driven formats to structured approaches targeting specific outcomes. The interventions are documented comprehensively to facilitate iterative improvement—locally and globally—and future scalability.

4. Cultural Game Jam Evaluation

The final phase involves empirical, experiential, and collective evaluation of the interventions towards follow-up opportunities for the QH Cultural Hub and the cross-cultural collaborations. CGJs are assessed based on feasibility, impact, and alignment with the Cultural Game Jam Context and its problem space, first at local sites and later in cross-European collaborations. Results inform redesigns, contributing to iterative cycles of improvement. To sustain impact, explore follow-on opportunities like continued development, partnerships, and dissemination.

This structured protocol synthesises DBR methodologies and the applied game jam framework, offering a practical guide to designing and iterating CGJs. Each phase also involves exploring and reconfiguring roles and responsibilities across sectors. It underscores the importance of collaboration, co-creative processes, context-sensitive knowledge and adaptability, knowledge production across sectors, follow-up opportunities, and iterative evaluation in achieving impactful and sustainable cultural innovation.

4. Youth Empowerment (YABs)

The EPIC-WE project seeks to empower youth citizens by involving them in cultural game-making activities that foster cultural, creative, and civic participation. The project aims to inspire and enable young people to engage with cultural and societal challenges through curiosity, creativity, agency, and imagination, collectively framed in the project as "Empowered Participation." Building on foundational theories of empowerment, the EPIC-WE approach draws insights from scholars such as Flanagan (2006), Murial (2021), and Tait et al. (2019), while emphasising game-making and gaming culture to enable empowerment and participation as both processes and outcomes (Pettit, 2012).

However, broader conceptualisation is necessary to deepen this framework and connect it to transformative youth participation in cultural and societal domains. As such, this protocol draws on a concept note on empowerment and empowered participation developed early in the project, where empowerment is conceptualised as both a process and an outcome, necessitating shifts in power relations, imagination, and active participation to reconfigure societal norms, institutions, and ideologies (Pettit, 2012).

Scholars such as Hardina (2008) and Kesby (2005) define empowerment as a multi-level process that fosters social change at individual, group, organisational, and societal levels. Kesby emphasises that empowerment cannot be externally imposed but must emerge through collective action that challenges societal power structures. Similarly, Sol (2019) highlights the importance of cultural participation in giving marginalised youth a voice to influence institutions. Kamruzzaman (2020) underscores the need to nurture critical consciousness and create inclusive decision-making spaces, while Morgan (2016) critiques depoliticised approaches that fail to achieve structural change. In the context of EPIC-WE, cultural game-making serves as both a medium and a metaphor for empowered participation, enabling youth to engage with cultural heritage in meaningful ways while developing competencies to imagine and shape a more inclusive future. By aligning with a democratised design agenda, EPIC-WE positions youth participation as a critical, creative process that reimagines cultural heritage and fosters collective care for societal renewal (DiSalvo, 2022).

In line with the EPIC-WE approach to empowered participation, Morgan (2016) emphasises that empowerment should extend beyond merely building skills and knowledge. He critiques empowerment initiatives that amplify people's voices without addressing the systemic inequalities that sustain their subordinate roles. Morgan highlights a common concern with such projects: the lack of meaningful structural change and the limited long-term impact on political and social systems (p. 176).

With these perspectives, EPIC-WE aims to enable and support youth's empowered participation in culture and society by securing their voices and engagement in both the project products (CGJs) and processes (research and innovation).

EPIC-WE has established and maintained Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) within and across its three QH Cultural Hubs. These boards enable young people (ages 16–25) to become equal partners in the quadruple helix innovation ecosystem. They contribute to the hubs' work in exploring, developing, testing, and evaluating interventions, participatory processes, research, and cultural innovation. Additionally, one YAB participant from each hub is invited to join the project's advisory board alongside experts in fields such as quadruple helix innovation, living labs, innovation, and game jams. In this setting, youth provide expert insights informed by their knowledge of youth culture and their experiences of cultural and societal engagement.

The members of the YABs are recruited from the project's CGJs, and they also have tangible lived experiences participating in those formats and processes, providing unique perspectives to the further innovation and research processes of EPIC-WE. Moreover, they are recruited with diversity in mind, entailing a mix of cultural, educational, gender, and experiential diversity. Later sections of this report elaborate on how universities, creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and youth collaborate equally to design, implement, and disseminate CGJs and new collaborative models. Finally, while each QH Cultural Hub has a Youth Advisory Board participating in the co-creative framework, a transnational YAB is also established with representatives from each local QH Cultural Hub's YAB, securing knowledge production and sharing across national borders and vastly different cultural backgrounds to strengthen youth empowerment and the project's research and innovation aims. This approach aligns with Morgan's (2016) argument that projects like EPIC-WE can and must empower and amplify youth voices while fostering structural change, demonstrating how large-scale EU initiatives can better integrate and prioritise the perspectives and experiences of young people.

5. Regarding Inclusion: Thoughts on Creating Inclusive and Enabling Spaces & Events

As a guiding principle of EPIC-WE CGJs, this practical protocol emphasises that all planning and decision-making should consider and aim to attend to the diverse needs of potential and registered participants, aiming to create inclusive – over inaccessible – spaces.

Regarding inclusion, it is essential to note that progress in creating more comfortable, enabling, and equal spaces is constantly changing. Therefore, whether it regards neurodiversity (ADHD, Autism, etc.), gender inclusion, or the enabling of different bodies, it is vital not to take for granted that work needs to be continually put in when endeavouring to create such spaces and that because of this, no “guide to inclusion” will ever be complete.

As such, this section aims to support finding the resources needed to create more inclusive spaces and how to evaluate their use cases, as opposed to prescribing a one-size-fits-all approach, which is antithetical to the work of connecting to the specific needs of the people being engaged.

The topics below are merely a few specific areas to consider when addressing inclusion. Racialisation, income, religion, and social class, to name just a few, are equally important. Like gender, bodies, and neurodiversity, each has its own set of particular questions, actions, supports, and so on, all of which should relate to the unique and individual needs of the person being engaged.

Regarding Gender

Particularly on gender inclusivity, a lot has changed over the last 10 years. With an increased focus on the inclusion of gender-diverse identities (non-binary, queer, bi-gender), language has an expanded role in accommodating their identities.

Here, a few well-known practices come to mind. Among them, “pronoun pins” serve as a good example of how to quickly and easily, with minimal cost, articulate a willingness to be inclusive. The function of a pronoun pin is similar to that of a name tag; they indicate what to call another person. On the surface, this serves two purposes. Firstly, it informs you about another person’s identity, though it is important to note that pronouns differ from gender identity. In this way, as organisers and participant collaborators, you can remain aware of any precarity that might accompany that identity. People with diverse gender identities are often documented as experiencing minority stress, leading to increased precariousness in their mental health due to this fact, and they are frequently positioned as subalterns, thereby facing minor verbal

abuse. In addition to informing each other of their positions, it also conveys to the individual that you care about their inclusion, which is crucial for establishing spaces for equal participation. This last aspect is, of course, dependent on the fact that this practice is not outdated; otherwise, it would suggest that an organiser's approach to inclusivity no longer aligns with contemporary practices.

Regarding Enabling Bodies

There is only one universal truth when it comes to differently abled bodies. That bodies are different. This also means that whilst general initiatives of bodily enabling can be taken, it is crucial to dialogue with participants who are differently abled about how they might be enabled or re-enabled to participate. Examples of general practices could be:

- Make sure all facilities are wheelchair accessible
- Make sure bathroom facilities are accessible for differently abled bodies
- Be aware of noise levels, sight reliance, or mobility reliance in your event and its activities
- Be mindful of the amount of walking required in your event, and how differently abled bodies might be able to navigate this

However, like with gender inclusion, doing these things in a manner that merely accommodates rather than enables or empowers does not set an inclusive tone for the event. For example, if people with mobility restrictions have to enter through the freight-entry or storage area because this is the only place with wheelchair accessibility, this affects these people. It is essential to re-enable not by necessity but through a willingness to dialogue, empower, and through making spaces that bring together instead of isolating.

Regarding Neurodiversity

Within disability studies and psychology, a lot has changed within the last few years. An emerging focus on inclusion in research has revealed that the diversity of how minds work is a strength rather than a weakness, at least when facilitated to be mobilised as such. Furthermore, critical studies have revealed that previous research has failed to acknowledge people with neurodivergence as mature and knowledgeable agents. From studies of linguistics to studies of psychology, these issues have meant that rather than enabling neurodivergent people, they have othered and victimised them.

For example, linguistics research has articulated the speech patterns recognised in autistic people as challenges they need to overcome. This pathologises autistic people and is exclusive and normative. An inclusive and enabling study would instead

examine how to facilitate a better understanding rather than correct the “wrongness” of autistic communication patterns.

Again, one way to combat this is to simply ask how neurodivergent people want to be included and re-enabled. Do they want to have “correct” speech patterns, or do they want to be understood?

How do we re-enable people with neurodiversities?

It is essential to be aware of different needs and to create a place and a space where individuals can communicate their neurodiversities and requirements to you. Encourage them to let you know if any methods work well in their support. Examples shared from the first two rounds of CGJs have included individual or quiet spaces where autistic people can take social breaks, quiet working areas that minimise stimulation, noise-cancelling headphones, and special chairs for those who need to stim while seated. Viewing these considerations as needs for enabled and empowered participation rather than mere wants is essential.

Additional Thoughts on Enabling Inclusivity

Numerous needs and experiences deserve consideration when facilitating equal, enabling, just, and ethically empowered participation. The examples offered above were specific inclusivity needs. What is shared below should be read more as approaches, ways of thinking, and actions that could be applied to a wide variety of people and their needs.

- Orient yourself in the current practices and language used around the group you want to include and be aware that your vocabulary might be outdated. A lot of websites and organisations have resources available. In Denmark, [LGBT+ Denmark](#) has articles on how to use pronouns correctly, such as [“Autisme-og asbergerforeningen”](#) (the Union for Autism and Asperger), which has resources on how to accommodate the needs of artists. It is important to note that when finding these resources, they should be “for-x-by-x”, meaning that if the organisation does not include people from the group about whom they are speaking, their knowledge becomes coloured and mispositioned.
- Check local resources, as they are more in touch with the contemporary culture and practices on a local level. However, if participants are advised to check out other resources, their lived experience and expertise take precedence over experts. After all, they are experts in their own life.
- Ask the individual about their needs. Individual ways to accommodate might be more inclusive and effective than attempting to find a one-size-fits-all solution.

- Document what works and, more importantly, what does not.
- Note that even if the activities and actions you take to include do not seem to work, they might still have the effect of creating inclusion. If the room dedicated to autists to take a break is not used, it doesn't necessarily mean that it was for nothing. The fact that the option was there might have been a comfort. Ask for feedback and trust what you are told.
- Disabilities, gender identities, and neurodivergence are private matters. Therefore, it is important to initiate private conversations about these topics.
- Inclusion is enabled through planning but actualised through flexibility. If needs arise, be ready to accommodate them.
- Ask how you can be accommodated instead of relying on others to ask you to be included or accommodated. Take the initiative to create inclusion and start the conversation rather than waiting for someone in a precarious position to start it.

Documenting Efforts Towards Inclusion

To continually develop the language and practice around inclusion, it is encouraged that each Hub notes their efforts towards inclusion in a table similar to the one shared below. In this way, EPIC-WE can create shared resources that work well in the particular context of CGJs.

Phase (pre-jam, during-jam, post-jam)	Description	Purpose
Pre-jam	In our sign-up formula we asked if there were any neurodivergencies or disabilities that we should be aware of. We also provided a text-box where people could add how we might accommodate these needs the best.	Locating critical points
During-jam	We provided a room (in this case a repurposed office) as a quiet space for an autistic participant to retreat to if they needed to do so.	Inclusion of neurodiversity

Post-jam	During the writing of an article, we asked our interviewees for their pronouns. And as one interviewee could not respond in time for the publishing of the article, we referred to them by name instead of pronoun.	Gender inclusivity
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The following Practical Protocol includes suggestions and ideas about inclusivity for the different planning and execution phases and topics. Please note that while these ideas have been shared, they are in no way exhaustive. The most crucial thing to harness is critical inclusivity thinking and action that connects with and attends to the specific needs of the people you are engaging with.

6. Cultural Game Jam Context

The CGJs which the EPIC-WE project organises distinguish themselves through a focus on culture. As stated under Section 2.4, the project integrates and innovates the principles of traditional game jams—short time frames, creative constraints, and public dissemination of game prototypes, emphasising culturally explorative and value-sensitive game design that promotes diversity, inclusivity, and empowered participation. Both local and glocal (thus national and transnational) with the cooperation of cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth participants (aged 16-25) to co-create games within and through cultural heritage settings.

Within this framework, the term culture is distinguished through three perspectives on games and culture: games as, for, and through culture, which:

... acknowledges the interplay between games and culture. It signifies that game-making and game-playing carry immense potential to act as value carriers and creators of culture, can be geared towards value-sensitivity, democratic participation, and diversity, and can shape societal transformation, policy, research, and innovation. They are the direct product of the CGJs. (Project Description D7.1).

The CGJ's essential task is to collaboratively define its purpose, objectives, and constraints—its problem space—through analysis and exploration. Drawing on literature reviews, partner expertise, and context-sensitive and cross-sector knowledge and experience, this phase identifies the specific challenges to address. It also sets clear criteria and problems to align the jam with cultural and societal goals.

6.1 Specificities of Developing a CGJ

The context of a 'cultural' game jam may differ from that of a 'regular' game jam. Though there are no set rules, the guiding principle of a CGJ is culture. As stated above, this unfolds in three ways. We respectively ask how we might operationalise game-making 1) *through* the use of cultural heritage during a CGJ, 2) how we might operationalise game jams as culture within a CGJ, and 3) how we might conceptualise the making of games *for* culture as the outcomes of a CGJ—with the overall ambition of conceptualising games as cultural expressions that can guide ideation, development, planning, running, and evaluation of future CGJs.

The focus is on culture, but this can mean many different things as a catchall term. The organisers of a particular CGJ must provide input on the kind of culture they want

to address during the CGJ, including its purpose, objectives, and constraints, i.e., its problem space.

A concrete example of such a problem space, which is used within the context of EPIC-WE, is a clear focus on using key values as defined by the European Union within the participating countries. These values are rights that the EU aims to hold up high within its borders. Examples of these values include democracy, equality and the rule of law. Participants of the CGJ are asked to integrate these values with a focus on a concrete subject (“theme”), such as polarisation in society. Also, they are tasked with using collections/heritage materials from the participating CHIs for their game concept. These objectives/constraints defined the problem space where participants are challenged to make their games. As said, these constraints may differ per cultural or applied game jam one wishes to organise. One can use tools to guide design and products during the CGJ towards specific outcomes.

Geared explicitly towards games through and for culture, specific cultural heritage collections have been used within CGJs. This combination creates a culture of making games, inputting culture within a cultural framework, and a triply layered exploration of using different sets or perspectives of culture supplied by the collaborating organising partners within the CGJ. Each of them has their own roles and responsibilities.

6.2 Roles & Responsibilities

Each quadruple helix partner serves a specific role within the QH Cultural Hub. This role translates to a particular set of responsibilities and practicalities leading up to and as part of the EPIC-WE CGJ that will be hosted in each QH Cultural Hub location.

Dividing the roles and responsibilities beforehand is crucial in achieving the most effective and complete intervention. Separating these other parts of the protocol and indicating how much staff is needed at what moment is essential for the smooth execution of the CGJs, particularly as the CGJs both involve YC creating games through and for culture, CHIs cultural innovation, CIs game innovation, and HEIs research and/or knowledge creation—all happening simultaneously and intertwined within the same CGJ. The roles and responsibilities range within various tasks and are not limited to the following examples. However, in general, we are dividing the practical running of CGJs into the Cultural Game Jam Design, Cultural Game Jam Intervention, and Cultural Game Jam Evaluation phases, each of which comes with different needs. While this approach has a generic and plastic potential to frame and conceptualise the CGJs across project sites, each QH Cultural Hub has navigated and approached the theoretical and practical planning with different inspirations, drawing from the

myriad expertise of the different hub partners and the individuals operating within them.

6.3 Networks

Mapping out the different networks per partner for the CGJ can be advantageous. Again, this differs depending on the kind of CGJ one wants to organise and what is needed. Here, EPIC-WE is an excellent example of varying partners 'meeting in the middle' to form a QH Cultural Hub and manage a specific type of 'cultural' Game Jam, which is not yet organised, as shown by the EPIC-WE Prisma2020 State-of-the-art Literature Review report.

Specifically working from the quadruple helix in developing these kinds of CGJ interventions, a layer of research through and on interventions (in EPIC-WE within a Design-Based Research framework) is added to the execution of CGJs, which facilitates the creation of knowledge for all quadruple helix partners. The specificity of the research methods used validates this way of working. Again, that is specific to the CGJ being made. Another CGJ might ask for a different approach depending on the goals set.

Lastly, a network might be necessary to 'get the word out' and reach and activate potential participants across sectors to engage with the CGJ. This network would also bring in additional expertise from external people to provide participants with various professional feedback perspectives.

6.4 Identifying & Framing the Problem

Central to the Cultural Game Jam Context is its 'Problem Space,' which defines the overall intention of the game jam. This means deciding which issue is at hand or which outcome is preferred. Putting the correct elements in place will set up the Design and Intervention phases to achieve results. Sections 6.1 and 7.2 state that the partners are asked to choose themes and constraints that enable a preferred outcome.

Within the EPIC-WE framework, for example, culture as an overarching theme has been concretised with constraints, such as integrating European values, societal issues, and a variety of cultural heritage collections, which differ per hub. This combined set frames the problematisation of culture within the CGJ, to which youth participants can provide solutions through the games they make during the interventions. Throughout Protocol 4, Lessons Learned are sections drawn directly from analyses created in T4.3 (local emphasis) and T2.4 (glocal emphasis) within EPIC-WE.

Lessons Learned:

1. **Balancing the Problem Space:** Using multiple sets of constraints can hinder their full use. Stacking, or giving too much to participants, can have the adverse effect of having them choose not to use them because, in essence, the problem space is too complex to be applied to the game being made.
2. **Abstract vs. Concrete Problems:** Sets of constraints, such as themes, must be on par with the level of thought of the participants. For example, most EU key values are on a level of abstraction, which makes it (too) difficult for certain youth to apply these within their games concretely. This may lead to the problem space being more or less bypassed by participants in favour of a game plan that meets their creative needs.
3. **Differing Cultural Heritage Collections:** Certain cultural heritage collections are more easily used or integrated into the game-making process during the CGJ than other collections. Constraints in time (as is often the case with game jams) and form might make it, for example, easier to integrate a painting as an object than, say, a collection of historical television news recordings that require time to dig into. Defining your problem space must align with the collections' usability towards participants if your set constraints are to be met.

Guiding Principles:

1. **Clarity of Theme & Constraints:** Clearly define the jam's theme, limitations, and any technical or creative constraints to provide focus without stifling creativity. Provide this to participants in the form of a clear and concise brief to set expectations (also see Section 7.2.1).
2. **Simplicity over Complexity:** Considering the above principles, one well-picked theme might work better within the breadth of imagination and interpretation than a set of themes and constraints.

7. Cultural Game Jam Design

As outlined in “Theoretical Framework for Game Jams in Applied Contexts” (Reid et al., 2020), the Cultural Game Jam Design phase focuses on structuring the event to effectively address the Problem Space, organising around two key aspects: “Guiding Criteria” such as themes or scenarios to direct game development, and “Logistics”, which manage practical considerations like duration, resources, and participant expectations to ensure a well-supported and realistic environment.

Overall, the design phase seeks to define an appropriate game jam format, which is developed through a definition of guiding criteria and logistics, and practical planning is required to facilitate this. While the below does not strictly adhere to Reid et al.’s Cultural Game Jam Design concept, it takes this as an influence and includes further considerations. Additionally, while there are specific areas that must be tackled in Cultural Game Jam Design, such as recruitment, deciding on the event theme, time constraints and timeframe, facility logistics, etc., it is difficult to assign a step-by-step order of tasks, as these things often need to be considered in tandem as they are interrelated. For example, suppose you choose to do open recruitment. In that case, this might mean that running an intensive jam over a weekend makes more sense as participants of a certain age will likely have school commitments during the week and, as such, would not be available then. This kind of open recruitment might afford more flexibility in devising a Jam theme, which would likely need to be advertised upfront to entice participants to sign up and might also require additional facilities such as sleeping places for late-night working. But suppose the decision is to work with an entire class cohort from an educational institute (for example, the hub’s educational partner). In that case, securing the class might mean holding off on deciding on a theme until it is clear what would be most useful to the class and aligning it to this. Such recruitment might also mean spreading a Jam out over a week or two to align it with the class schedule, and it might also mean being able to split facilities across the CHI partner and the participant’s school, where additional facilitators from the school might be available to support the jam.

In event planning terms, one might consider the Cultural Game Jam Design phase akin to the pre-production phase of event planning, making decisions and devising processes, scheduling and preparing to execute the event (Cultural Game Jam Intervention). Such Cultural Game Jam Design considerations that need to be worked out in advance of the Intervention should include but are not limited to establishing a timeframe for the Jam, selecting a theme and creating a schedule of facilitation activities that align with the timeframe and the CGJ Kit phases and other considerations as outlined in Protocol 2 of this deliverable, deciding on a recruitment approach and enacting that strategy to recruit, scheduling and prepping facilitators, deciding on and

gathering materials and equipment provided to participants for digital design or paper prototyping, deciding on the setup of workspace and the booking of all rooms including additional “chill-out”, quiet working or sleeping spaces, planning and arranging food and drinks for the event, setting up communication channels for the participants to discuss and collaborate, preparing materials and print-outs for any and all event or activity facilitation.

While this document aims to support the practical execution of a CGJ, different considerations or decisions will need to be made based on the specific CGJ at hand, its partners, the location and the needs of the participants, paying attention to inclusivity considerations for each part, of the process, as discussed in Section 5 and spoken to across this document. However, there are various broad topics that will almost always need to be considered for each game Cultural Game Jam Design phase. Below is a roundup of these, including guiding principles and lessons learned.

7.1 Recruitment of Participants

Recruitment can be one of the most challenging parts of hosting a Game Jam. How will participants be recruited to accommodate the diversity and inclusion of different sectors (HEI, CHI, and CI), different local sites and contextual themes, and across genders, ethnicities, ages, abilities and experiences?

There are multiple ways to recruit YC participants for the CGJs, depending on which type of CGJ one wants to organise and to what end. Consider resources that can help reach large groups with relevant expertise and interests within the domains of games and culture that fit a specific demographic. Examples could be using certain social media platforms to reach a particular audience (for example, Facebook will be more relevant to an older demographic, and TikTok will be more appropriate to a younger one). This can be decided and worked with the chosen communication strategy by recruiting specific HEI students/groups on the network linked to the HEI partner or by activating the Youth Advisory Board as recruitment ambassadors. The approach and focus will differ per partner attached to a CGJ Hub: secondary HEI partner, art schools or academies, universities, vocational institutions, etc. However, it is essential to clarify what organisers articulate or facilitate and what is expected of the YC participants regardless of the specific group being recruited. A clear “What’s in it for me?” value proposition helps interest participants.

Recruitment of participants gives the organiser a choice in steering the CGJ towards a specific outcome, i.e., game design/development students in higher education will yield different levels of finished games and cultural emphasis or problematisation than students in secondary school, or those deeply involved in video game culture

and coding will more likely produce video games versus paper prototype forms by other participants. Within the context of EPIC-WE, there is a clear overall focus on YCs within the age range of 16-25 years (however, the age range might differ within each CGJ depending on how recruitment is done. For example, open recruitment could yield results across the age range, whereas specifically recruiting from a second-year HEI programme would tend to yield participants at the older edge of that spectrum.

Depending on the interests, resources, and networks of the QH Cultural Hub, decisions regarding how to recruit YCs for a CGJ will vary. Different recruitment strategies will also create distinct dynamics during the CGJ and necessitate various types of facilitation. For instance, a QH Cultural Hub could aim to recruit a cohort of CGJ participants by bringing in an entire class from the HEI partner whose curricula focus on related topics, or teachers within the HEI partner could be engaged to publicise the CGJ widely in their institutions, promote it in specific departments or courses, or conduct more personalised outreach to recommend the CGJ to particular students. Alternatively, open recruitment might be conducted where basic demographic parameters, such as age range, are specified. Still, other than that, the call is open to anyone wishing to register as long as they meet the criteria. Even within open recruitment for a CGJ, it is crucial to prioritise diversity within the recruiting pool. For instance, the Aarhus QH Cultural Hub within EPIC-WE decided to recruit their participants following the specifications below:

- Aim for 50/50-representation from art/culture and games/programming/design
- Emphasis on recruiting people of all genders/all humans
- Divide the game jams across different age groups:
 - age 20-25 for Cultural CGJ 1
 - age 16-21 for Cultural CGJ 2

The work of successful recruitment should not be underestimated. QH Cultural Hub needs to begin making decisions about its recruitment approach months in advance of the scheduled CGJ, with timing allocated should a new strategy or approach be required.

7.1.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

Lessons Learned:

1. **Authentic Community Engagement Supports Recruitment:** Partnering with schools, youth organisations, cultural groups, and creative partners makes it easier to build trust and participation. These connections provide credibility, extend outreach, and foster deeper engagement, as the CGJ's topics and approach already resonate with potential participants.
2. **Accessible and Youth-Friendly Communication Matters:** Effectively reaching youth requires meeting them where they are. Platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and Discord facilitate direct engagement, making recruitment efforts more visible and interactive, especially for Open recruitment.
3. **Incentives Encourage Participation:** Offering mentorship, networking opportunities, prizes, and the potential for further development of a selection of games raises interest. These incentives clearly provide tangible benefits that make participation more appealing.
4. **Clear “Value Proposition” Enhances Appeal:** Highlighting skill-building, creativity, and social impact makes the event more meaningful. Participants are likelier to commit when they understand the personal and professional benefits.
5. **Word-of-Mouth is a Powerful Recruitment Tool:** Encouraging past participants and Youth Advisory Board members to act as ambassadors amplifies outreach. Firsthand experiences resonate more with potential participants and help build enthusiasm.
6. **Educator Support Expands Reach:** Engaging teachers and program leaders from HEI partners and other education networks helps attract larger groups. Educators serve as trusted advocates, introducing the opportunity to students. This is especially true for classes already engaged in CGJ-related themes.

Guiding Principles;

1. **Youth-Led Promotion:** Actively involve the Youth Advisory Board (YAB) in recruitment efforts by encouraging them to promote the event within their schools and youth networks.
2. **Broad & Inclusive Outreach:** Expand recruitment (especially for open recruitment) beyond game design and innovation students to include participants from diverse disciplines such as visual arts, cultural studies, storytelling, and media studies. Strive for gender inclusivity and cultural diversity.
3. **Extended Recruitment Timeline:** Allocate additional time to reach and engage a wider and more diverse audience.
4. **Engaging Visual Promotion:** Use compelling images and videos from past CGJs (CGJs) to make event promotions more persuasive and impactful.
5. **Youth-Centric Approach:** Design recruitment materials and processes that resonate with youth, ensuring that registration is simple and accessible.

6. **Pre-Event Information Sessions:** Organize sessions for participants in the case of open calls and/or schools, teachers, and students for school-facilitated recruitment to clarify expectations and answer questions about participation.
7. **Clear Participation Guidelines:** Provide expectations such as a Game Jam Brief and necessary release forms well in advance to give participants time to review and ask questions.
8. **Cultural Sensitivity and inclusion:** Ensure all promotional materials and recruitment activities reflect diverse identities and experiences. Recruitment sign-up forms should openly ask participants to share any specific needs they might have, such as: “Do you have any learning, mobility, sensory, identity or other needs that we should be/need to be/you’d like us to be aware of?”
9. **Tech & Digital Accessibility:** Use mobile-friendly and easy-to-navigate platforms and tools to streamline sign-ups and participation.
10. **Centralised Communication Hub:** Discord should be maintained as the primary communication platform to foster engagement before, during, and after the event.
11. **Sustainability & Growth:** Foster a long-term, engaged community by building a network of past participants across the CGJs, opening invitations to participants to join the YAB or connect with past participants as ambassadors of upcoming CGJs.

7.1.2 Steps: Recruitment Snapshot

A diverse and engaged group of participants enhances the Jam’s success.

1. **Outreach & Promotion:** To spread the word, use social media, game development forums, related university programmes, and university groups of the HEI partners. Also, the YAB should be activated to support peer recruitment.
2. **Registration System:** Set up an easy-to-use online registration form to gather participant details.
3. **Provide Resources and/or Pre-Event Sessions:** Offer toolkits and documents and Jam Brief in advance of the Jam and, where possible, pre-event sessions to onboard participants and answer any questions they might have.
4. **Release Forms:** Ensure that expectations of participant involvement are clear and that release and other legal forms are written in an easy-to-understand way. Share these forms with participants before the Jam to accommodate any additional time they might need to understand them, ask questions, and sign them.

7.1.3 Inclusivity Considerations

- Actively promote the event to underrepresented groups in game development.
- Offer financial assistance and/or travel reimbursement to participants with limited resources.
- Ensure materials and instructions are available in multiple languages where possible.
- Provide multiple communication channels (text, voice, video) to support different communication preferences and needs.
- Ensure the registration process is straightforward and accessible for individuals with cognitive disabilities.
- Ensure the inclusivity arrangements for facilities and facilitation are advertised in recruitment materials so students with diverse physical, learning and neurodiversity needs feel invited to apply.
- Specifically, ask about needs on registration forms in an open way.

7.2 Jam Format

A well-defined game jam format is essential for creating a structured, engaging, and accessible participant experience. The format establishes clear expectations, ensuring that participants of all skill levels can effectively contribute and innovate within a given timeframe. By setting parameters such as duration, team size, thematic scope, technical and material constraints options, and judging criteria, organisers can guide creativity while maintaining a fair and inclusive competition – if the event is competitive.

When defining a CGJ's format, the QH Cultural Hub should consider the aims of the CGJ at hand, and the demographic of Youth participants recruited. Is it designed to encourage rapid prototyping in a sprint format, or is there a slower process at hand? How will the format affect the ability of participants to explore cultural narratives, and in what ways does the format encourage or limit the possibilities of youth empowerment? Answering these questions helps determine key elements such as the time limit (e.g., 48-hour, week-long or more spread-out jams), the size and composition of teams, and what development tools or materials are allowed. Additionally, selecting an engaging theme, ensuring accessibility for diverse skill levels, and providing clear guidelines for the final games developed are crucial for maximising participation.

Additionally, as noted above, the timeframe requires other considerations: What impact will the timeframe format have on recruitment possibilities? Are there timing specifics that need to be identified based on the needs of those being recruited or the timing and availability needs of the location where the jam is being hosted?

Community engagement is another essential factor. Providing communication platforms (e.g., Discord or forums) fosters collaboration while incorporating playtesting or feedback sessions improves the quality of entries. The QH Cultural Hubs may also implement structured judging criteria through a panel of experts and/or participant voting to fairly assess creativity, technical execution, adherence to the theme and other criteria. Ultimately, a well-structured format sets the foundation for a successful game jam, ensuring a balance between creative freedom, challenge, and inclusivity.

7.2.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

Lessons Learned:

1. **A Clear Jam Brief Outlining the Timeframe, Scope, Focus and Expectations of the Jam, Pitch Guidelines and a Clear Overview of Jury Criteria for Judging the Final Games Supports Participants in Developing Culturally-Related and European Value-Relevant Games:** Providing participants with a clear overview of the focus of the game and what is required of them helps set clear expectations. The format of a clear and concise Brief helps set the scope for participants. Providing Pitch instructions that connect back to the Jam Brief and the Jury Judging Criteria ensures that participants know what they are expected to present in their Pitches. Sharing the criteria that the Jury will use to judge the final game Pitches, which is connected to the expectations laid out in the Brief and Pitch Instructions, is a way to help reinforce the aims of the CGJ, make clear what participants are working towards, and what is expected in terms of a final game. For example, an overview of such jury criteria could include:
 - 1. THEME: Does the game help young people engage with the thematic topic of the Game Jam?
 - 2. STORY OF THE GAME: How does the game's story provide an innovative and creative experience for the player?
 - 3. GAME MECHANICS: How playable is the game prototype? Is there still a lot of work to be done, or can it be "sold" as is?
 - 4. CULTURAL MATERIALS: To what extent is the game concept or other aspects of the game inspired by, or incorporates, the cultural materials introduced to the participants?

For an example of Game Jam Brief, see APPENDIX I; for an example of Pitch Prep Instructions, see APPENDIX II; and for a detailed example of judging criteria and grading scale, please see APPENDIX III.

Please note that sharing requirements and criteria does not guarantee that all groups will follow the brief strictly, and there will likely be different scales and approaches to involving cultural materials or incorporating European Values into the games.

2. **Providing a Communication Hub Boosts Engagement:** A central place (e.g., Discord) enhances collaboration and troubleshooting.
3. **Jams with Participant Voting Can Become Popularity Contests:** If using participant voting, consider balancing it with a diverse pool of expert judges.

Guiding Principles:

3. **Clarity of Theme & Constraints:** Clearly define the jam's theme, limitations, and any technical or creative constraints to provide focus without stifling creativity. Provide this to participants in the form of a clear and concise brief to set expectations.
4. **Time Management:** Set a reasonable time frame that balances creativity and execution (e.g., 48 hours for intense jams, spread over a week or a week intensive). The time frame developed needs to align with the recruited participants and will likely determine whether the Jam takes place over the weekend or during the week, as well as the time frame.
5. **Tool, Engine and Material Agnosticism:** Support a wide range of digital tools, engines and paper prototyping materials to accommodate different skill sets and preferences.
6. **Community & Collaboration:** Foster a supportive, collaborative environment through communication platforms (e.g., Discord).
7. **Fair & Transparent Judging:** Ensure clear, fair criteria are shared with participants and relate back to the Jam brief already shared. Make sure to have a diverse pool of judges.

7.2.2 Steps: Defining the Jam Format Snapshot

Before launching the event, determine its structure and format. Consider the following:

1. **In-person, Online, or Hybrid:** Decide whether participants will meet physically, virtually, or both.
2. **Size and Formation of Teams:** Establish the size of the teams and how they will be formed (e.g., randomly based on skills, interest in specific themes, etc.)
3. **Duration:** Set the timeframe (e.g., 24 hours, 48 hours, a week, or a month-long slow jam).

4. **Technical & Material Constraints:** Determine which game engines, tools, digital assets or physical materials are permitted.
5. **Submission Requirements:** Define the format in which final games should be submitted (e.g., playable builds, source code, design documents, paper prototype).
6. **Develop Judging Criteria:** Based on the details outlined in the Brief, develop criteria for the Jury upon which they will judge the final games.

7.2.3 Inclusivity Considerations

- Ensure accessibility features for virtual events, including captions and screen reader support.
- Provide clear, easy-to-read documentation with alternative formats (audio, video, or simplified text) for neurodiverse participants.
- Offer structured guidance and checklists to assist individuals with different learning needs in navigating the event.

7.3 CGJ Content: Processes, Phases, Methods & Tools

The instruction and framework of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit played a large part in developing the event content. This CGJ Kit outlines the processes, phases, methods and tools for creating and running a CGJ. Within the EPIC-WE project, it is expected that all QH Cultural Hub partners will work with the phases and draw from the methods and tools developed in the CGJ kit, but that there is, of course, flexibility to attune the Jam to the particular QH Cultural Hub context, including the possibilities afforded based on the QH Cultural Hub particular constellation of YC, CHI, CI and HEI partners and facilities at hand.

Protocol 2 of this deliverable provides a detailed overview of the CGJ processes, phases, methods, and tools.

7.4 Thematic Choice

Selecting the right theme is essential for a CGJ, especially when participants must draw inspiration from a cultural collection and engage with one of the European Values. A well-defined theme sparks creativity and ensures that games reflect meaningful cultural narratives while fostering innovation and empowerment. A strong theme encourages participants to explore heritage locations, artistic works, historical media materials, and all other forms of cultural heritage in ways that resonate with contemporary audiences. By connecting cultural heritage with game mechanics, storytelling, and design, participants can create experiences that educate, entertain, and

inspire. Additionally, linking the theme to a European Value—such as human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, or respect for cultural diversity—ensures that the jam contributes to broader social discussions.

When selecting a theme, organisers must consider how well it integrates with the cultural collection used as material and inspiration. Additionally, if closed recruitment occurs by connecting with a specific university programme or secondary school class, it will likely need to align with the foci of those particular cohorts. Themes should encourage thoughtful engagement with the cultural sources while remaining flexible enough for diverse interpretations. The theme should also be inclusive, allowing youth participants from varying backgrounds and skill levels to participate meaningfully. Furthermore, involving participants in selecting the theme or refining their specific angle within a broader theme can increase excitement and ensure it resonates with them. The first two rounds of EPIC-WE CGJs saw several themes offered to participants:

Cultural Game Jam #1

- Aarhus: Human Nature
- Óbidos: UNESCO City of Literature
- Hilversum: Mental Health and Climate

Cultural Game Jam #2

- Aarhus: Modern Art (1960-present)
- Óbidos: Sustainability and Biodiversity – Óbidos Lagoon
- Hilversum: Media & Democracy

Across the QH Cultural Hubs, the Local CGJ themes were selected due to their ability to intersect with and offer inspiration from the cultural collections offered for participants to engage with at that jam, that they provided space to explore the European Values in different kinds of ways, and ideally resonated with the pool of participants recruited.

7.4.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

Lessons Learned:

1. **Defining the Jam Theme is a Balance:** A too-focused and prescribed theme might not spark the interest or creativity of participants, but a too-broad theme also runs the risk of participants finding it hard to focus. A slightly focused

theme sparks creativity better than a fully open-ended one and offers interesting and open ways to engage with European values and the cultural collection at play.

2. **Cultural Context Matters:** Participants may need guidance on historical or artistic materials to engage with the theme effectively. Too much material to work with can lead to overwhelm, but too little might not encourage creativity. The material's format also requires considering how it is introduced and used within the jam. For example, AV content might take longer to engage with than 2-dimensional artworks.
3. **Diversity in Interpretation Strengthens Engagement:** A flexible theme allows for different perspectives and allows youth participants to incorporate their experiences and interests into the topic.

Guiding Principles:

1. **Encourage Cultural Exploration:** The theme should inspire participants to engage deeply with the chosen cultural collection.
2. **Connect with a European Value:** It should align with or encourage the possibility of connecting with, questioning, and incorporating key European values such as democracy, diversity, or freedom to foster meaningful storytelling.
3. **Support Multiple Interpretations:** The theme should be broad enough for different genres and game styles.
4. **Balance Accessibility and Depth:** It should be easy to understand but offer layers of meaning for deeper engagement.
5. **Ensure Relevance to Youth Audiences:** The theme should link cultural heritage with socially relevant issues or perspectives for Youth Citizens.
6. **Connect the Theme to the Youth Being Recruited (Where Applicable):** If a school or university programme is being recruited for the CGJ cohort, speak with the class's teachers and find ways to connect the theme to the interests of the school and its students.

7.4.3 Inclusivity Considerations

- Choose themes that are broad enough to allow different cultural and personal interpretations.
- Avoid themes that might be exclusive or inadvertently offensive to marginalised groups.
- Encourage open discussions about the theme to ensure all participants feel comfortable engaging with it.

- For participants with different processing styles, provide multiple ways of engaging with the theme, such as written descriptions, visual representations, and spoken explanations.

7.5 Jam Schedule of Activities & Facilitation

The EPIC-WE CGJs designed and facilitated by each QH Cultural Hub use the processes, phase planning, methods, and tools outlined in Protocol 2 of this document. Depending on the format defined and the participants, each CGJ will require different considerations in terms of scheduling and facilitation.

A well-structured schedule and facilitation strategy are critical to the success of a CGJ, ensuring that participants can maximise creativity, collaboration, and productivity while exploring the defined theme, effectively incorporating cultural materials into their work and engaging with European Values. As described in Protocol 2 of this document, the EPIC-WE CGJ progresses through distinct phases—Phase 1: Experience, Phase 2: Play, Phase 3: Imagine, and Phase 4: Create—each having a different aim, with different methods to choose from, and different transition tools to employ between phases. While the overall design of a CGJ follows the processes as outlined in Protocol 2, there are still several decisions to be taken on the part of the QH Cultural Hub in terms of schedule and facilitation, such as given the time frame of the event, how much time will each phase/activity be allocated; how will ice breakers, warm-ups, breaks and cool downs be scheduled; what kind of timing is allocated for testing, feedback, etc; how will facilitators engage with participants etc. Each phase and activity of a CGJ requires different levels of focus, skills, guidance, and support. Planning a schedule that aligns with the CGJ phases helps participants manage their time effectively and encourages a structured yet flexible workflow.

Effective facilitation methods, such as structured check-ins and progress-tracking moments, and participant communication tools, such as Discord, help participants navigate challenges. As suggested in feedback to the CGJs #1 and #2, the Jams should be hosted both by a Creative facilitator (supported by the CI partner of the QH Cultural Hub, and perhaps also the HEI and CHI partners, depending on their individual expertise) and Cultural Facilitator (supported by the CHI Hub partner) at all times, to be able to provide support and guidance to participants about both game development and the cultural materials they are expected to engage with.

A well-thought-out plan prevents common issues like scope creep, participant fatigue, uncertainty about time use, and lack of direction, ensuring a smoother and more enjoyable experience for everyone involved.

Please see APPENDIX IV: CGJ Event Schedule with CGJ Phases—Example for an example of a CGJ event schedule concerning the CGJ phases.

7.5.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

Lessons Learned:

1. **Technical Issues Can Disrupt Progress:** Encourage participants to test prototypes early and often, whether a digital or physical game, to avoid last-minute crashes for digital games or unexpected faults in paper prototype games.
2. **Encouraging Playtesting Improves Game Quality:** Mid-jam feedback sessions, such as the Expert Council transition tool between the Play and Imagine phases, help teams refine their mechanics.
3. **Breaks & Health Matter:** To prevent overwhelm or burnout, encourage pauses, hydration/food, and a “work-life” balance (especially for 48-hour sprints). It is also key to have quiet spaces away from the main Jam area for participants to decompress.
4. **Documenting Helps Growth:** Ensuring participants document their process on Itch.io is integral to the EPIC-WE project and supports participants in learning from the experience. To make sure participants understand its importance, spend time describing the purposes of documenting and integrating the process into the Jam activities so it is not thought of as an optional or after-thought task by participants.
5. **Cultural Context Matters:** Allowing for adequate time to engage with cultural materials and having access to cultural facilitators throughout the Game Jam, and not just during certain phases, supports participants in understanding the cultural collections they are engaging with and allows for more depth of inspiration and/or integration in their games.
6. **Collaboration Challenges Should be Addressed and Supported:** CGJs often bring together diverse teams, requiring clear communication and cooperation strategies. Encouraging teamwork strengthens creative problem-solving and inclusivity. It is important to take time to address collaboration challenges should they arise and support the teams in finding their own solutions.

Guiding Principles:

1. **Time Management:** To prevent rushed or unfinished projects, allocate clear time blocks for each phase, the methods to be used within each phase, and the transition tools. Also, schedule breaks and other kinds of warm-up, cool-down, and connection moments.
2. **Flexibility:** Allow for adjustments in the schedule to accommodate unexpected challenges.

3. **Maintain Focus on Cultural Materials:** Strengthen the facilitation of cultural materials by integrating related activities throughout the event, including before the CGJ and during the different Phases. For example, include criteria about incorporating cultural materials in the Jam Brief and a description of their use in the Pitch and Jury criteria that examine the use of cultural content.
4. **Youth Advisory Board Facilitators, Expert Council and Jury Members:** Engage the Youth Advisory Board (YAB) as facilitators, expert council members and jury members to foster a peer-to-peer dynamic and strengthen the Quadruple Helix Model by positioning youth as active contributors rather than passive end users.
5. **Creative and Cultural Facilitators:** Plan for both Cultural and Creative game-making facilitators to be present throughout the entire event, not just during specific phases.
6. **Diverse Representation is Key:** Ensuring facilitators and mentors reflect diverse cultural and professional backgrounds fosters inclusivity and openness.
7. **Facilitation Balance:** Offering facilitation is a balance. Pay attention to the different needs of the different groups in terms of facilitation. For groups that need less facilitation, ensure that it is not offered as an invasive element of the process. Ensure greater access to cultural and creative facilitators in a way that fosters an environment where participants feel empowered to seek help voluntarily rather than being overwhelmed by unsolicited feedback. Plan for more informal moments during the CGJ to create a relaxed atmosphere where participants might feel more comfortable asking for help and sharing ideas with facilitators.
8. **Feedback and Iteration:** Encourage continuous playtesting and feedback loops using the different phase methods and transition tools to support this.
9. **Breaks and Well-Being:** Incorporate downtime to prevent overwhelm/burn-out and maintain creativity (especially for 48-hour Jams and other sprint formats)
10. **Game Development Documentation:** Clearly articulate why documentation is necessary for participants and try incorporating documentation moments into the Jam activities to emphasise their importance.
11. **Cultural Sensitivity:** Ensure the respectful and informed use of cultural collections.

7.5.2 Inclusivity Considerations

- Plan for inclusive facilitation strategies that accommodate diverse needs and settings. Tailor approaches to provide both general and individualised support, recognising the varying skill levels and competencies of participants and their groups.

- Ensure showcase and judging formats do not disadvantage those with disabilities or language barriers.
- Structure activities with clear expectations, written summaries, and visual timelines for neurodiverse participants.
- Include scheduled breaks for meals, rest, and prayer times.
- Use simple, clear, and jargon-free language in facilitation and documentation.
- Provide written and visual aids for better comprehension.
- Foster a welcoming and respectful environment with clear codes of conduct.
- Support different skill levels by encouraging mentorship and pairing beginners with experienced participants.
- To help everyone feel comfortable, provide icebreaker activities that are sensitive to the group's needs (e.g., gender non-confirming participants or neurodiverse participants).
- Allow anonymous reporting of harassment or discrimination.
- Provide resources on designing for accessibility (colourblind-friendly palettes, subtitle options, etc.).
- Encourage teams to consider representation in characters, narratives, and mechanics.
- Offer guidelines on ethical storytelling and avoiding harmful tropes.
- Support diverse playtesting groups for feedback.

Encourage open discussions while moderating for respectful dialogue.

7.6 Facilitation Materials

CGJ facilitation materials are resources designed to support the QH Cultural Hubs cultural and creative facilitators in running the Jam and support CGJ participants in engaging and deepening their involvement in the process. Facilitation materials can take many formats, from ideation printouts and brainstorming prompts to game activity materials meant to inspire team creativity and event books that provide a roadmap and schedule for the event ahead.

For facilitators, these materials offer essential tools for planning, organising, and running a smooth event. They help set expectations, guide discussions, and foster an inclusive, creative environment. For participants, facilitation materials serve as prompts, frameworks, and references that can spark ideas, streamline collaboration, and ensure a relationship to the CGJ theme, the cultural collections they engage with, and European Values in their games.

Based on the methods and tools a QH Cultural Hub uses in the different phases of the CGJ, based on the processes shared in Protocol 2 of this document, materials that the QH Cultural Hub develops might broadly include:

- **Event booklet with a daily schedule** to set expectations and illustrate what is coming ahead.
- **Jam Brief. Pitch Prep Instructions and Jury Criteria** to highlight what is expected of participants and how their work will be evaluated.
- **Activities and game handouts** will familiarise participants with the cultural collection they are engaging with and give them context and inspiration.
- **Theme prompts and idea-generation tools** to help participants explore cultural topics.
- **Game design frameworks and worksheets** to structure brainstorming and prototyping.
- **Mentorship guides and discussion prompts** for engaging deeper with cultural themes.
- **Time management templates, schedules and checklists** to help teams stay on track and complete their Itch.io documentation

For examples of different facilitation materials, please see examples of different CGJ playbooks (practical collections of processes and methods to communicate the CGJ Kit) in APPENDIX V: CGJ Participant Event Booklet - Example.

7.6.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

- **Roadmap of the Event and Materials:** A roadmap (Practical Playbook or production schedule) of the CGJ event schedule and the materials participants will receive helps teams and individuals stay organised.
- **Clear Expectations:** The Written Jam Brief, Pitch Prep Instructions, and Jury Criteria help participants focus on the CGJ's aims and expectations.
- **Clarity and Accessibility:** Materials should be easily understood and available in multiple formats. Clear guidance and reference materials help facilitators and participants navigate the game jam effectively.
- **Structure and Flexibility in Materials:** Participants appreciate structured but flexible resources that support creativity.
- **Encouraging Creativity:** Activities and prompts should inspire rather than restrict participants.
- **Collaboration-Oriented:** Resources should support teamwork and knowledge sharing.
- **Preparing & Printing Materials:** It always takes longer to develop, design and print materials than expected. Leave a significant amount of lead time to minimise last-minute stress on the part of organisers.

7.6.2 Inclusivity Considerations

- **Language Accessibility:** Provide materials in plain, clear language.
- **Representation:** Include diverse cultural perspectives in examples and resources.
- **Disability Access:** Ensure materials are compatible with screen readers and provide for alternative-sized printed formats.

7.7 Design Materials, Tools & Technology

Organising a CGJ requires careful preparation of both digital and physical tools to support diverse creative processes. The tools used in the Game Jam will be related to the Jam Format, for example, whether participants are developing digital games, physical games or have the space to choose what they would like to design. For digital game development, essential technological tools include pre-installed computers with game engines and image and animation asset creation software. Version control systems and cloud storage solutions should be set up to facilitate collaboration. Audio tools and free sound libraries are also helpful. High-speed internet, extra peripherals (mice, keyboards, drawing tablets), and charging stations ensure smooth development and reduce the possibility of minimal tech snags causing significant delays.

For paper prototyping, materials should include cardstock, markers, sticky notes, scissors, dice, modelling clay, and game tokens. These materials allow participants to be creative in developing physical games. The selection of materials should balance cost, sustainability, and accessibility while encouraging creativity.

Organisers should clarify before the Game Jam what participants must bring and what will be provided, such as personal laptops or drawing tablets, and offer loaner devices if required. Providing a packing list is helpful, especially if participants are expected to stay overnight for a sprint format and might also need to bring more personal items like sleeping bags, etc.

7.7.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

- **Mixed Materials Allow for Creativity:** Consider a mix of digital and physical materials to support different types of game development, creative interests and workflows. Provide adaptable, open materials that allow creativity beyond pre-defined formats.
- **Different Skill Levels:** Plan for various participant skill levels, offering beginner-friendly options.
- **Make Participant Packing List Clear:** Provide a clear participant packing list upfront that illustrates what tools and materials participants are expected to

bring. The list should also specify whether participants are expected to have any pre-installed engines, apps, or accounts available on their computers.

- **Provide Backup and Loaner Equipment:** Have extra equipment available for backup and offer loaners to participants who might not have personal access to specific equipment.

7.7.2 Inclusivity Considerations

- Provide accessible devices and screen readers for participants with these needs.
- Have devices and equipment available to loan should participants not be able to provide it themselves.
- Ensure gender-neutral and culturally inclusive assets if provided by the organiser, or make a critical reflection on the lack of them part of the work of the Jam.

Accommodate different skill levels with tutorials and beginner-friendly tools.

7.8 Facilities & Space Design

Arranging a facilitation space for CGJs requires careful consideration of logistics, accessibility, and participant needs. The space should encourage creativity, collaboration, and engagement with cultural materials. Key decisions include venue selection, layout, and available resources.

Facilities to Consider and Prepare:

- **Workspaces:** Ensure ample seating, desks, and breakout areas for teams to collaborate comfortably, all with easy access to electrical outlets.
- **Quiet Workspaces:** As stated in 7.8.2, provide quiet, low-stimulation workspaces for neurodiverse participants and participants with different focus needs.
- **Technology:** Provide high-speed internet, charging stations, and access to game development software and other tools.
- **Materials:** Provide easy and open access to paper prototyping materials close to the workspace.
- **Presentation Areas:** Designate spaces with projectors and sound systems for pitches and showcases.
- **Rest and Refreshment Zones:** Include lounge areas and access to food and drinks.
- **Sleeping Areas:** For overnight Jams, provide a quiet, dark, designated sleeping area.

- **Cultural Materials Display:** Depending on the cultural materials being engaged with (physical sites, artworks, AV materials), decide how and where they will be displayed or accessible. Near the workspace, ways to continue to “visit” or “engage” with the cultural materials should be provided.

7.8.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

- **Reliable Power and Internet are a Must:** A stable power supply and high-speed Internet are crucial for uninterrupted development and collaboration. Without them, work can be delayed, and participants may become frustrated.
- **Flexible Spaces Enhance Collaboration:** A mix of open workspaces and quiet areas allows teams to collaborate effectively while providing individual space to focus. Adjustable and movable furniture helps adapt the environment to various needs.
- **Prioritise Participant Comfort & Accessibility:** Comfortable seating, adequate lighting, and accessible facilities make the event more inclusive. Ensuring the space is wheelchair-accessible and has comfortable and adjustable furniture helps everyone stay engaged.
- **On-Site Technical Support Prevents Disruptions:** Having IT personnel available ensures that technical difficulties can be swiftly resolved. This prevents lost time and allows participants to stay focused on their projects.
- **Clear Signage Improves Navigation:** Well-marked areas help participants quickly find essential facilities, reducing confusion and saving time. This is especially important in large or unfamiliar venues.
- **Balance Work and Relaxation Areas to Provide for Different Needs:** Dedicated lounge and break areas, with access to drinks and food, allow participants to rest and recharge. Ensuring a healthy balance between work and relaxation boosts creativity and productivity.

7.8.2 Inclusivity Considerations

- **Accessible Entrances, Seating, and Restrooms:** Ensure all pathways, seating arrangements, and restrooms are wheelchair-accessible and comply with accessibility standards to accommodate individuals with mobility challenges.
- **Gender-Neutral Restrooms:** Providing gender-neutral restroom options promotes inclusivity and ensures comfort for all participants.
- **Quiet Spaces for Neurodivergent Participants:** A designated quiet area helps participants who may be sensitive to noise or require a calm environment to focus and decompress.
- **Consideration of Dietary Restrictions in Food Provisions:** Clearly label all food options and provide a variety of meals that cater to common dietary needs, including vegetarian, vegan, gluten-free, and allergy-friendly options.

- **Visual and Hearing Accessibility:** Include closed captions on presentations, offer assistive listening devices, and provide printed materials in large print or Braille to accommodate participants with visual or hearing impairments.

7.9 Developing the Research Plan

An EPIC-WE CGJ has an additional execution layer related to researching the Jam. Within the current QHE framework, the higher education partner is responsible for this task. As the research activities are directly related to the CGJ's schedule, many QH Cultural Hubs consider the design of the jams' creative/cultural activities and their schedule, along with decisions, planning, and timing regarding possible research opportunities. To understand the EPIC-WE Research Protocol comprehensively, please see Protocol 3, which is dedicated to research design and part of this deliverable.

Research involves planning and execution. Deciding on research activities, when they will take place, and who will run them from within the team must align with the CGJ schedule of activities and should also be noted on the overall production schedule. Additionally, close coordination with the QH Cultural Hub partner responsible for the CGJ venue is integral to ensure there are appropriate facilities for all research activities (for example, a quiet room to record interviews).

7.10 Roles & Responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities of each partner in the Cultural Game Jam Design phase of a CGJ are flexible and depend on the specific needs of the event being organised. Factors such as location, participant demographics, jam format and thematic focus all influence how these roles are organised. While the below provides a general framework, the actual division of responsibilities should be determined collaboratively by the different partners of the QH Cultural Hub and concerning the specific needs of the event being organised.

For example, if a jam is hosted at the QH Cultural Hub partner's site, they would likely take a more prominent role in arranging and preparing the CGJ facilities, whereas if the hosting takes place across both the QH Cultural Hub and HEI partner locations, facilities preparation and logistics would most likely be more shared. Or, for example, a game jam focused on digital game development will likely rely more heavily on the CI partner for technical tools and workflows, whereas a jam emphasising physical prototyping might see greater contributions from both the CI partners and other partners with experience in hands-on crafting and storytelling techniques.

With this flexibility in mind, the list below outlines each partner's general roles and responsibilities in the different design topics of a CGJ. These should be adapted based

on each event's specific goals and context. These are not fixed, and expertise is often not solely owned by one partner. As a QHE operating in a collaborative hub format, input and responsibilities frequently traverse specific partner types. Below are just suggestions of possible scenarios.

1. Participant Recruitment

Each partner plays a vital role in attracting a diverse group of participants:

- **Creative Industries Partner** reaches out to game developers, artists, and designer networks to promote the game jam.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** connects with their education department to find relevant participant pools.
- **Higher Education Partner** engages educators to connect with relevant programmes and courses to promote the game jam.
- **Youth Partner** ensures outreach to young participants via schools, youth groups, and social media.

2. Deciding the Game Jam Format

The following offers an overview of the specific expertise of the different partners. That said, education expertise often stems from the educational departments of the QH Cultural Hub partners, while ideas for educational activities and the authentic integration of cultural materials may derive from the CI partner.

- **Creative Industries Partner** suggests structures and activities based on industry-standard game jams.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** ensures that the format properly integrates the cultural materials.
- **Higher Education Partner** balances the format with research and educational needs.
- **Youth Partner** provides input on accessibility and engagement for younger participants.

3. Choosing a Jam Theme

For example, in choosing a theme for the CGJ, the:

- **Creative Industries Partner** brings expertise around developing an effective theme that aligns with the goals of a CGJ.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** ensures the theme connects with the cultural collections/materials available.
- **Higher Education Partner** aligns themes with research goals.

- **Youth Partner** ensures themes resonate with young audiences and encourages creative storytelling.

4. Developing a Jam Schedule of Activities

A well-planned schedule ensures smooth execution:

- **Creative Industries Partner** offers possible workflows based on expertise with design sprints, hackathons, and game jams.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** ensures the schedule includes engagement with cultural materials and heritage-related discussions to support the inclusion of these materials in the games.
- **Higher Education Partner** offers research-driven methodologies and participatory design frameworks and ensures research activities align with the jam schedule.
- **Youth Partner** ensures a dynamic and engaging experience suited to young participants.

5. Developing a Facilitation Plan and Assigning Roles

Facilitation needs to be carefully planned. Within the CGJ structure, it is vital to have both a creative facilitator and a cultural facilitator available to participants during the jam.

- **Creative Industries Partner** leads creative brainstorming and game design sessions. It is available for game design support.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** introduces cultural materials and is available to support the incorporation of those materials into game design.
- **Higher Education Partner** provides instruction and support in dev log documentation and the use of Itch.io – and is also present as a researcher.
- **Youth Partner** ensures youth-driven facilitation for peer engagement.

6. Designing and Preparing Facilitation Materials

Facilitation materials should be engaging and well-structured:

- **Creative Industries Partner**, with the QH Cultural Hub, designs and provides content for programme booklets, handouts, activity sheets, etc.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner**, with the QH Cultural Hub, designs and provides content for programme booklets, handouts, and activity sheets and prepares all cultural materials for the jam.

- **Higher Education Partner**, with the QH Cultural Hub, develops educational resources and information on documentation/Itch.IO activities required of participants.
- **Youth Partner** ensures materials are accessible and engaging for youth participants.

7. Deciding on and Preparing Digital & Physical Prototyping Materials

A mix of digital and physical tools enhances creativity:

- **Creative Industries Partner** selects digital game development tools and, along with the **Cultural Heritage Partner**, **Higher Education Partner**, and **Youth Partner**, ensures access to a wide variety of open-ended and user-friendly paper prototyping materials.

8. Arranging and Preparing the Game Jam Facilities

The event space should be functional and welcoming. Most real pre-production work will likely fall to the institution hosting the event in their space. In the context of EPIC-WE, this has fallen mainly to the QH Cultural Hub partner. However, decisions around setup, the “vibe” of the working space, and logistical questions are often collaboratively determined by the hub.

- **Creative Industries Partner** suggests setup ideas for the CGJ working space.
- **Cultural Heritage Partner** ensures heritage elements are available in the CGJ working space.
- **Higher Education Partner** setup research-related materials and tools.
- **Youth Partner** ensures a youth-friendly environment with accessible work-spaces.

8. Cultural Game Jam Intervention

8.1 Cultural Game Jam Intervention

Cultural Game Jam Intervention is the overall practical implementation of a CGJ, the real-time execution of the jam, where the QH Cultural Hub supports and facilitates participants to actively collaborate, design, and develop games within a limited timeframe based on a theme and connected to specific cultural materials. This is where the CGJ phases, methods and tools are executed as outlined in Protocol 2 of this document. The Cultural Game Jam Intervention serves as the core period where ideas transform into tangible game prototypes, allowing participants to apply their skills in real-time problem-solving and iterative design. Effective facilitation, coordination, and technical support are essential to ensuring a smooth production workflow and keeping QH Cultural Hub partners clear on their defined roles within the CGJ and participants engaged and motivated. Organisers must anticipate challenges such as time constraints, technical issues, and cross-team communication hurdles.

Maintaining a structured yet flexible approach allows the game jam to remain productive while allowing space for creativity. Various topics fall under Cultural Game Jam Intervention, from the production aspects, such as arranging workspaces, testing technology, and setting up physical prototyping materials, to managing guest experts and organising and managing the food and drinks available to the participants. The intervention also includes executing the actual CGJ Phases, Methods and Tools, running the QH Cultural Hub-designed programme, and supporting participants by completing and pitching their game prototype. A well-executed Intervention phase based on thoughtful and clear Cultural Game Jam Design results in a diverse set of game prototypes that deeply engage with both the jam theme and the cultural materials and provide the right conditions for youth empowerment to flourish.

1. **Venue & Tech Setup:** I oversee the setup and maintenance of the CGJ's physical spaces, such as workspaces with different stations prepared and ready for each team, quiet workspaces, a rest and refreshments room, quiet spaces for participant interviews and testimonial recordings, etc. Furthermore, test and ensure internet stability, equipment functionality, and the availability of all necessary paper prototyping materials.
2. **Technical Support & Troubleshooting:** Have facility IT support for any facilities-related tech issues (i.e., lighting, projectors, heating, internet issues, etc.). Furthermore, have tech support on hand from within the QH Cultural Hub to provide real-time assistance for software installations, hardware issues, etc., to prevent teamwork disruptions.

3. **Facilitation Materials:** Ensure that all printed and other facilitation and activity materials are available for participants.
4. **Live Schedule Management:** Monitor the event timeline, give reminders to facilitators, adjust for delays, and ensure key deadlines are met.
5. **Release Forms:** Confirm all participants have signed the various release forms.
6. **Participant Assistance & Wellbeing:** Address participant concerns, provide logistical support, and ensure a safe and inclusive environment.
7. **Expert Guest Hosting:** Assign an expert guest host from within the team. Re-confirm expert guests' arrival on the day of, track their arrival, re-brief them as they arrive, ensuring they know what the plan is and what is expected of them, and “manage” them while they are there.
8. **Real-Time Communication & Updates:** Ensure Discord is set up for the CGJ, that it is clear for participants what channels to use, and maintain clear, ongoing communication through the event over Discord as a centralised communications space.
9. **Communication/Promotion During Event:** Manage live social media updates, photography, and community interactions to generate interest in the event and have materials to showcase the CGJ.
10. **Event Research:** Ensure research partners have decided on their research activities and have all the materials required to execute them. Also, ensure they are clear on their research schedule and that all equipment is present, tested, and set up (such as a camera for recording interviews).
11. **Games Documentation:** Ensure that all games have been adequately documented on Itch.io and that each game has clear photographic and, ideally, video documentation.
12. **Post-Jam Wrap-Up & Documentation:** Gather participant feedback, document key takeaways, and manage any follow-up communications or project continuation opportunities.

Behind any Cultural Game Jam Intervention, there needs to be a well-organised QH Cultural Hub that includes the CH, CI, HE, and YC partners of the QHE. Assigning roles and responsibilities during the Jam is essential. To ensure organiser roles are clearly defined (whether it be behind-the-scenes logistics, upfront facilitation, or research and documentation activities), it is recommended that the QH Cultural Hub collaboratively develops a Production Schedule that all organisers and facilitators are familiar with and have a copy of to follow during the jam.

Please see APPENDIX VI for an example of CGJ Event Organisers' Practical Playbook (production plan)

8.1.1 Lessons Learned & Guiding Principles

Lessons Learned:

1. **Proactive venue and tech setup prevent disruptions:** Ensuring different workspace zones are fully set up, tested, and functional before the jam starts minimises disruptions and stress.
2. **Dedicated technical support is crucial:** Having both facility IT support and game development-specific technical support available prevents major disruptions during the event.
3. **Clear schedules and reminders keep things on track:** Regular updates to facilitators and other QH Cultural Hub members from a dedicated person assigned to monitor and manage the schedule support facilitators in staying on time, help participants maintain momentum, and ensure deadlines are met.
4. **Release forms should be shared and signed before the event, allowing for smooth documentation.** Ensuring all participants complete the required forms early prevents issues with content sharing and research activities.
5. **Effective expert guest hosting enhances engagement:** Having a dedicated host for guest experts ensures they feel welcomed, informed, and properly integrated into the event.
6. **Real-time communication improves participant experience:** A structured Discord setup and continuous updates create a centralised space for announcements and troubleshooting.
7. **Real-time and post-event communication create long-term impact:** Live event coverage boosts visibility and helps future iterations of the CGJ gain attention.
8. **Proper research planning supports meaningful insights:** Deciding on research activities and coordinating researchers in advance ensures all required materials and equipment are ready and functional and that the CGJ will be properly documented as a research intervention.
9. **Too many QH Cultural Hub people present, and too much documentation can make participants feel uncomfortable and like they are “being observed”:** Pay attention to the specific needs of the CGJ participants as a group and individually. Too many QH Cultural Hub people present can create a feeling of “being observed” and “scrutinised”, and too much photography throughout the event can make participants feel uncomfortable and disrupt focus.
10. **Thorough game documentation preserves and enables showcasing the games created:** Ensuring all games are fully documented with dev logs on Itch.io and with photos and videos of the gameplay allows understanding of the game development and proper showcasing of the game for the games resource website and potential future development for the selected games.

Guiding Principles:

1. **Be proactive, prepared and responsive:** Anticipate logistical challenges and have contingency plans in place to handle potential disruptions. Enough spontaneous requests or problems will pop up: Be responsive to unexpected technical or material requests.
2. **Provide clear instructions:** Provide participants with clear instructions, such as printed guides and/or a dedicated space on Discord for accessing specific tools, cultural materials and Itch.io.
3. **Foster clear and open communication:** Utilize structured communication channels, such as Discord, for streamlined coordination and participant support.
4. **Ensure inclusivity and accessibility:** Design spaces and materials that accommodate diverse needs, including quiet workspaces and accessibility-friendly environments.
5. **Maintain structured flexibility:** Follow a clear schedule while allowing room for adaptability and on-the-spot changes to meet participant needs and unexpected deviations from planning.
6. **Document:** Take photos, videos, and participant testimonials of both the event itself and the final game prototypes to have a variety of materials to draw from for promotion, research, reflection and future development. But pay attention to the specific needs and feelings of the group in terms of how much and how documentation is created so as not to make them feel uncomfortable or pull focus from their game-making work.
7. **Prioritise participant well-being:** Offer rest areas, schedule meal breaks, and ensure a supportive and positive atmosphere.

8.2 Roles & Responsibilities: Cultural Game Jam Intervention

Running the CGJ requires a well-structured approach, with clearly defined roles and responsibilities to ensure smooth facilitation, technical support, participant engagement, and documentation. Each partner within the QH Cultural Hub contributes their unique expertise, ensuring that the event runs efficiently and effectively integrates cultural heritage into the creative process.

However, these roles are not fixed and can vary depending on each game jam's specific context, venue setup, and hosting arrangements. Whether the event occurs on-site at a cultural heritage organisation, an academic institution, or a different venue altogether, responsibilities may shift based on available resources and logistical considerations. Flexibility and collaboration are key, allowing partners to adapt their contributions to best serve the needs of participants and create a meaningful cultural game-making experience. Below is a breakdown of the key CGJ production topics and a general idea of the roles and responsibilities that partners could take.

1. Creative & CGJ Facilitation

- **Creative Facilitation Led by:** Creative Industries Partner
 - Facilitates brainstorming, ideation, and rapid prototyping sessions based on the planned schedule of activities.
 - Ensures teams incorporate cultural heritage elements effectively.
 - Encourages innovative storytelling and game mechanics through feedback and mentorship
- **Cultural Facilitation Led by:** Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Provides an introduction to cultural materials and historical or cultural context to support accurate use within game design.
 - Offers insights on the cultural materials.

2. Venue & Technical Setup (e.g. hosted at a CHI partner location)

- **Led by:** Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Secures and manages the physical venue of the CGJ
 - Ensures venue logistics, such as seating, workstations, and accessibility needs.
 - Arrange food/beverages and ensure all CGJ prototyping and other materials are available.
- **Supported by:** Creative Industries Partner
 - Assists in workspace layout to optimise creativity and collaboration.
- **Supported by:** Higher Education Partner
 - Provides insights on venue needs based on research/documentation setups.

3. Technical Support & Troubleshooting

- **Led by:** Creative Industry Partner
 - Ensures participants have access to necessary software and hardware.
 - Provides troubleshooting for technical challenges.
 - Helps manage digital collaboration tools
 - Assists with game engines, design tools, and workflow integration.
- **Supported by:** Hosting Venue
 - Provides technical support concerning facilities, such as Wi-Fi access, power stations, etc.

4. Facilitation Materials

- **Led by:** Creative Industries Partner

- Prepares materials such as creative guides, templates, and best practices.
- Ensures accessibility of resources for diverse participants.
- **Supported by:** Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Provides cultural reference materials, artefacts, or historical sources.
- **Supported by:** Higher Education Partner
 - Contributes academic research insights for deeper engagement.

5. Live Schedule Management

- **Led by:** Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Oversees overall event timing and transitions.
 - Ensures smooth coordination between activities and breaks.
 - Manages time allocation for presentations, mentoring, and feedback sessions.
- **Supported by:** Creative Industries Partner
 - As creative facilitators, assist in time management

6. Release Forms

- **Led by:** Higher Education Partner, Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Ensures all participants sign necessary agreements regarding intellectual property, media consent, and research participation.

7. Participant Assistance & Wellbeing

- **Led by:** Creative Industry and Cultural Heritage Partners - as facilitators and production managers
 - Monitors participant wellbeing and provides a support system.
 - Organises breaks, relaxation spaces, and mental health support.
 - Creates an inclusive and welcoming environment.
- **Supported by:** Hosting Venue
 - Ensure accessibility considerations regarding the venue and logistics.

8. Expert Feedback & Expert Guest Hosting

- **Led by:** Creative Industries and Cultural Heritage Partners
 - Coordinates expert feedback sessions and jury deliberations.
 - Host guest experts as they arrive.
- **Supported by:** Youth Partner
 - Participates in feedback sessions and jury, offering insight and feedback to CGJ teams and individuals.

9. Real-Time Communication & Updates

- **Internal Team Led by:** Cultural Heritage or Creative Industry Partner
 - Provides logistical updates on the event schedule and changes.
 - Manages internal team coordination via Slack, Discord, or other channels.
- **CGJ Participants Led by:** Cultural Heritage or Creative Industry Partner
 - Provides logistical updates on the event schedule and changes.
 - Manages CGJ participant communication channels (e.g. Discord) to share such updates.
- **Supported by:** Youth Partner
 - Assists with two-way communication between participants and organisers.

10. Communication/Promotion During Event

- **Led by:** Creative Industries Partner
 - Manages storytelling, media presence, and social media content.
 - Engages the public with event highlights, live streams, and interviews.
- **Supported by:** Higher Education and Cultural Heritage Partner
 - Documents event activities for research dissemination.

11. Event Research

- **Led by:** Higher Education Partner
 - Sets up materials and tools for research collection
 - Communicates research activities to participants
 - Executes research
- **Supported by:** Youth Partner
 - Assists in research activities, such as observations or gathering qualitative insights through participant interviews.

12. Game Documentation

- **Led by:** Higher Education Partner
 - Facilitates and supports participants in documentation dev logs on Itch.io
 - Ensures participants complete dev logs on Itch.io
 - Ensure proper recording of game prototypes and gameplay.
 - Collects all game paper prototypes at the end of the CGJ.
- **Supported by:** Creative Industries Partner
 - Helps bring documentation moments into the facilitation of the CGJ.

13. Post-Jam Wrap-Up & Documentation

- **Led by:** Higher Education Partner
 - Produces case study documentation on the game jam's research activities, research outcomes, and key learnings.
 - Organise a post-event debriefing session.
- **Supported by:** Youth Partner
 - Provides key feedback from the youth perspective on the execution and experience of the CGJ.

9. Cultural Game Jam Evaluation

Evaluating CGJs requires a nuanced, reflective, and multidimensional approach that considers both immediate outcomes and long-term effects. Given their role within QH Cultural Hubs—cross-sector partnerships that cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, universities, and youth citizens collaborate to create meaningful cultural interventions within a cultural-creative context—evaluation should extend beyond surface-level metrics to explore the transformative potential of these events. This entails understanding their impact on cultural participation, collaborative innovation, sustainable creativity practices, and youth empowerment.

CGJs are more than mere game development events; they act as catalysts for cultural engagement and creative experimentation. Their evaluation must, therefore, encompass the broader implications of the jam’s design, execution, and follow-on opportunities (Reid et al., 2020). Key questions include: How do these jams empower participants as cultural co-creators? What role do they play in fostering new cultural narratives? How do they facilitate collaboration or enable empowered participation across disciplines and sectors - and within cultural spheres?

One of the vital challenges in evaluation is balancing immediate, formative insights with summative reflections on long-term impact. Formative assessments should examine how participants interact, develop ideas, and engage with cultural themes during the jam, while summative evaluations should explore the sustainability of projects, knowledge transfer, and continued collaboration among stakeholders. Furthermore, evaluators should remain mindful of the Hawthorne effect, as the QH Cultural Hubs dual role as facilitator and evaluator might influence outcomes.

Evaluating CGJs necessitates a collaborative effort that bridges expertise across multiple sectors, fostering a rich exchange of knowledge and innovation. Cultural heritage institutions bring a profound understanding of storytelling, art, exhibitions, and audience engagement, enabling games to meaningfully reinterpret cultural narratives. The creative industries contribute technical and artistic expertise, integrating game design, programming, and immersive storytelling to craft engaging experiences. Higher education institutions provide research-driven methodologies, participatory design frameworks, and humanities-based approaches, fostering critical reflection and knowledge production. Meanwhile, young citizens offer fresh perspectives on engagement, empowerment, and the role of cultural heritage in gaming culture—and vice versa, actively shaping content through QH Cultural Hubs and youth advisory boards. By blurring the lines between research, practice, and innovation, these hubs become spaces for epistemic partnerships—where expertise converges

to co-create knowledge and cultural products. This approach embraces cultural innovation as an evolving process shaped by the interplay of local life, sectoral contributions, and collaborative creativity—working towards broader empowered participation within and across sectors and partners.

Assessing the effectiveness, relevance, and significance of various CGJ structures—fixed, flexible, or freeform—is crucial for understanding how they promote cultural creation. This evaluation should encompass an analysis of how well the jam’s structured phases (Experience, Play, Imagine, Create) enable participants to transition from inspiration to tangible game concepts. Key transition tools, such as the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council, play an important role in this process by refining participants’ ideas and ensuring cultural relevance and thematic depth. Evaluators should also consider the long-term impact of CGJs, particularly their contributions to fostering cultural curiosity, generating new interpretations of heritage, and supporting sustainable game-making practices beyond the event itself. By incorporating these dimensions into the evaluation process, CGJs can be more effectively recognised as transformative platforms for cultural expression and innovation. This method guarantees that evaluations yield significant insights into the immediate creative outputs and the broader impact of these events on cultural participation and creative ecosystems.

9.1 Recommendations for Evaluating CGJs in Local & Glocal Contexts

CGJs operate within both local and glocal (global-local) spheres. While local relevance ensures that the outcomes of the jams resonate with specific communities, practices, and cultural institutions, their broader significance lies in their ability to generate scalable insights. To evaluate the jams effectively across these contexts, consider the following recommendations:

Local Evaluation Strategies:

- Examine how the jam fosters meaningful engagement with local cultural narratives, practices, and heritage institutions.
- Assess the extent to which game concepts integrate and reinterpret local cultural heritage in ways that resonate with the community and connect across European values and youth empowerment through game-making.
- Capture participant reflections on their creative, cultural, and relational experiences, emphasising collaborative processes and cultural exchange.

Glocal Evaluation Strategies:

- Identify and refine transferable design principles that can be adapted across different cultural and local contexts.
- Assess the accessibility and adaptability of jam outputs in international and cross-cultural settings, ensuring collaborative, ethical and culturally sensitive engagement.
- Encourage ongoing knowledge-sharing through open-access documentation, public showcases, and cross-sector dissemination strategies.

QH Cultural Hub Strategies:

- **Foster Transdisciplinary and Cross-Sector Collaboration:** Evaluate how different stakeholders—including cultural institutions, universities, creative industries, and youth citizens—contribute to and benefit from the jam and how they experience (dis)empowerment, belonging, and cultural innovation.
- **Integration, Preservation, and Transformation of Cultural and Technological Practices:** Examine how digital tools and game design approaches within cultural heritage contexts support or challenge cultural engagement, creative expression and empowered participation.

Within a Design-Based Research framework, evaluation should focus on the scalability of outcomes, ensuring that insights from one jam contribute to broader discussions on game-based cultural engagement. Generalisation from specific case studies should emphasise key design principles and methodologies that can inform future projects worldwide.

9.2 Principles for Evaluating CGJs

A structured yet flexible evaluation framework should incorporate the following principles:

A collaborative and culturally grounded evaluation framework could benefit from considering the following principles:

- **Sustainability, Cultural Transformation, and Future Impact:** Consider the longevity of projects beyond the jam, including how they foster ongoing cultural engagement or belonging, community ownership, and cross-sector partnerships. Identify pathways for continued development, including funding opportunities and institutional support.

- **Cultural and Contextual Adaptability:** Evaluate and refine design principles to diverse cultural, social, and local-glocal contexts. Consider how local narratives can be transformed into globally relevant insights—and how principles derived from a CGJ may apply across diverse settings.
- **Collaborative Knowledge Creation:** Reflect on how the event promotes shared learning, co-creation, and mutual exchange among participants, cultural institutions, and creative industries. Investigate how knowledge flows within and beyond the jam through mentoring, peer-to-peer learning, and expert guidance.
- **Participant Empowerment and Relationality:** Assess how participants develop creative agency, strengthen collaborations, and establish meaningful relationships across disciplines, sectors, and cultures. Include reflections on their evolving role as cultural co-creators and empowered, participatory citizens.
- **Design Robustness and Cultural Resonance:** Analyse how game prototypes and concepts integrate cultural themes, heritage, European values, artistic expression, and game-making in an innovative and meaningful way to participants and audiences – and, furthermore, how game-making becomes culture-making.
- **Games through and for Culture:** CGJs create cultural games that might be either *through* or *for* culture. *Games through culture* use cultural heritage as innovative game-making material to enable new aesthetic expressions, actualisations, and remediations of cultural heritage and game design. *Games for culture* engage broader cultural and societal contexts by creating games with and for cultural value, transformation, and empowered participation.

By adopting this comprehensive framework and adapting it to various contexts, CGJ evaluation can enrich our understanding of their role as vehicles for cultural expression, participatory engagement, and creative innovation. Moving beyond event-centric assessments, this approach ensures that CGJs can develop a lasting impact on participants, cultural institutions, and the broader quadruple helix ecosystem.

10. Local/Glocal Cultural Game Jam Design

The local-glocal perspective is particularly relevant to the EPIC-WE project, where culture is understood in terms of higher education institutions, creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and broader regional identities. These dual cultural perspectives are essential in understanding "glocal" exchanges, where local cultural influences shape global frameworks. This underscores the significance of regional strategies in global game development efforts.

The findings of the EPIC-WE state-of-the-art report reveal the complex interplay between global and local forces in game jams. They demonstrate how local cultural policies can shape and enhance global participation. In this way, "glocal" game jams emerge as sites where local cultural contexts influence and enrich global game development practices.

From this interplay comes the concept of *glocal culture*, which combines global and local elements, reflecting how global influences interact with and adapt to local cultural practices, histories, and lived spaces (and vice versa). The term "glocal" is derived from the contraction of "global" and "local." It emphasises the idea that in today's interconnected world, global trends and cultures often blend with local customs, resulting in unique cultural forms (see, for example, Kjeldgaard & Askegaard, 2022; Popov et al., 2019). *Glocalisation* in education and culture represents an alternative to internationalisation, emphasising a reflexive exchange of global and local knowledge rather than acculturation (Patel & Lynch, 2013). Consequently, the concept of glocalisation, however still an emerging concept, is related to, e.g., hybridisation, creolisation, and mixtures (Roudumetof, 2015), emphasising an in-betweenness of global space and local place.

The "local" in this sense is not always tied to a specific place. Instead, it can represent a socially constructed or imagined space, entailing that the local and global are not binary opposites, as global influences often shape the local. This broader understanding aligns with the idea of the "glocal." Glocal studies see the local-global relationship as mutually constituent, entangled, and interplaying, with a place/space emphasis on creating new social places and spaces within a resolution of the antithesis of space and place. Specifically related to youth culture and citizenship, Kjeldgaard and Askegaard (2005, p. 233) state that "the styles characteristic of youth culture spread globally, instigating the development of local versions of youth culture through appropriation and creolization", which connects to the above emphasis on the global influences on local space and place—that localisation is always imbued by globalisation and, as such, continuous processes of glocalisation. Through a cultural perspective, a glocal approach might support a transition from cultural aware-

ness to intercultural awareness that reflects the vast contemporary mobility and cultural diversity that currently calls for viewing culture as an in-between space that still supports local (though multiple) identities.

Glocalisation, as an emerging concept and practice, is a space-place demarcated by its in-betweenness of global and local, the ever-present interplay of global culture on local culture, of global tendencies on local practices—and vice versa. A glocal approach is spatially ill-defined, something neither here nor there, though connected to both local and global cultures, environments, knowledges, and tendencies.

According to the three EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs, the term "glocal" captures the dynamic interplay between global and local contexts, emphasising the integration and adaptation of global ideas, strategies, processes, materials, and influences within local environments. The concept underscores the importance of addressing global challenges through localised actions (and vice versa) in ways that respect and incorporate traditional cultures and values. It embodies the principle of thinking globally and acting locally and encourages cross-border collaboration by tailoring global solutions to local needs.

To put these concepts into practical action and design a game jam within a glocal framework, steps can be taken to create a space/place for interaction and ideation between the local and the glocal. Potential steps to organise a glocal game jam might include:

1. **Developing global themes** (e.g., societal or cultural issues) shared across the QH Cultural Hub that can be adapted locally. A local interpretation of a global theme will differ in interpretation per hub or CGJ organiser, which enables the creation of a variety of perspectives and views on issues.
2. **Developing local themes** (e.g., particular cultural themes or problems stemming from local cultural heritage) applied in glocal processes (where other hubs “jam” with other hubs’ local themes. A locally sourced theme or cultural heritage might be interpreted differently per region, which makes for new perspectives on this theme.
3. **Creating shared challenges passed between teams across countries.** These challenges may be the same per hub or a linked challenge in which the continual solving of these challenges is asked of participants per hub to bring it to a successful close at the end of the link.
4. **Hosting synchronous events where local and remote participants exchange feedback** on, e.g., game design processes, ideation, playtesting, or the final

expo where game prototypes are showcased. This synchronicity enables a focus of ideas and output around differing local interpretations of themes to create perspectives on a glocal level.

5. **Hosting asynchronous events where local and remote participants exchange feedback** (as above but not taking place simultaneously).
6. **Establishing cross-hub mentorship programs or expert sessions.** An exchange of perspectives and knowledge to enable local information to be sourced by other hubs.
7. **Forming cross-hub youth advisory boards.** Enabling participating youth to exchange ideas with other QH Cultural Hub and all four partners within those hubs, strengthening the interconnect between participants, partners and hubs.
8. **Engaging youth participants in online pre-event discussions.** A great way to create pre-fun for the CGJ itself and a possibility to already start exchanging views and ideas about themes, game concepts and designs. A communicational notebook of ideas and excitement.
9. For example, to extend European collaboration among youth jammers and share ideas and game prototypes or concepts, a Discord environment that is open to youth participants from all EPIC-WE CGJs could be created. This environment, featuring a user-friendly interface that facilitates communication about CGJs, could facilitate preliminary discussions.

11. Directions for Future Research & Innovation (Additional Scope)

Future research and innovation in designing, facilitating, and evaluating CGJs should investigate several key avenues to enhance inclusivity, impact, and sustainability. One promising direction is the integration of youth in shaping interventions and collaborations through active participation in advisory boards, both local and global, as well as through other participatory methods. By engaging youth in these ways, CGJs can better reflect diverse perspectives and empower the next generation of creators.

Inclusive, pluriversal, and transversal design considerations must be central to the future development of CGJs as a format and approach to ensure that the diverse experiences, values, and cultural backgrounds of participants are meaningfully represented in the design process, thereby promoting a more equitable and inclusive environment. However, more significant and profound knowledge and experience are needed regarding different design approaches—from a practical perspective—and how these impact CGJs, participant experiences, design considerations and outcomes, and roles and responsibilities within the collaborative partnerships.

Moreover, the inclusive design of CGJs extends beyond youth participation during them; it is also before and after and how to create opportunities for youth empowerment here, while it further connects to the potentials and tensions that might arise in different contexts through CGJ interventions. It, for example, relates to how cultural heritage institutions, art spaces, archives, and so on can transform into co-creative laboratories for CGJs, as well as the constraints, contingencies, and challenges that must be considered. Future innovation and development of CGJs should explore and navigate the various rhythms, routines, contextual dependencies, and practices to support and strengthen CGJs as a profoundly sustainable and meaningful cross-sector approach.

Another area of focus is the quadruple helix innovation ecosystem concept, which emphasises the balance and integration of various sectors. Further exploration of cross-sector co-creative partnerships within the context of cultural innovation can provide valuable insights into how these collaborations can be nurtured and sustained to promote more innovative and inclusive CGJs. Future research and innovation endeavours would, moreover, benefit from further testing and reflection on CGJ materials, tools, approaches, and stakeholders.

Ultimately, there is a need for research that critically evaluates the differences between local and glocal CGJs. Does the glocal approach truly offer distinct outcomes

compared to its local counterpart, or is this distinction primarily theoretical? Investigating how the glocal approach is practically realised within the context of CGJs and what changes it might bring about will provide valuable insights into its potential benefits and challenges. Research in this area should also explore how these changes can be effectively measured and evaluated to ensure the glocal approach delivers and fosters global-local synergies in cultural innovation across practices, domains, sectors, regions, and nations.

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13. Appendices

APPENDIX I: Jam Brief - Example

Below is an example of a CGJ Brief. This document is developed to ensure that participants have an overarching understanding of the event, their participation, and what is expected of them as participants.

Game Jam Brief

In this CGJ, you will go through four phases and combine four elements: art and culture, European values, game design, and citizenship. You will design a value-based cultural game prototype and/or concept based on at least one European value, a cultural heritage material, and relate it to a societal challenge. During the jam, you will move through four different ideation and development phases: experience, play, imagine, and create, with a transition tool aiding the move from one phase to another.

The overarching theme of this CGJ is “**That’s Not Fair**”, which emphasises that inequality is not merely an obstacle—it is the very foundation of numerous systems that shape our lives. These imbalances affect how we access resources, interact with others, and envisage our future. As the European Union grapples with increasing polarisation and crises related to climate, housing, and the cost of living, understanding fairness is now more crucial than ever. By exploring themes such as the wealth gap, social inclusion, and climate justice through games and culture, we encourage young game-makers to ignite more profound, playful, and empathetic conversations about what equality truly means to youth today.

This means that your team will design and deliver a value-based and cultural game:

- As a **game concept and/or prototype**
- That integrates at least one of the **European values**
- And is inspired by at least one piece of **cultural heritage material**
- Which connects to **youth citizenship**, highlighting your voices and broader perspectives on culture and society
- Connects to the jam theme: “**That’s Not Fair**”
- That is uploaded to the **platform itch.io**
- With **game logs** from each of the four phases showing your process and reflections.

You will also:

- Prepare a 5-minute pitch about your game following the pitch guidelines & evaluation criteria shared

APPENDIX II: Pitch Prep Instructions - Example

The following offers text that could be used in Pitch Prep Instructions tailored to the specifics of the QH Cultural Hubs jam. These instructions support participants in preparing for their pitches. Pitch prep instructions are also useful as they outline for students what is expected of them regarding the things they should have considered and developed in their game concept/prototype.

Pitch Prep Instructions

Time to prepare a pitch for your cultural game concept.

A pitch is a short and engaging presentation that clearly explains why your concept is unique. The pitch should excite the audience about the game and its possibilities.

Use the following steps to prepare an engaging pitch of about 5 minutes. The following topics should be covered:

1. Theme & Values

How does your game align with the theme of the game jam?

Explain how the theme “*That’s Not Fair!*” is reflected in the game through the storyline, challenges, and interactions. Show how the theme is integrated into the game mechanics and objectives.

2. Concept

Story, goal, and characters

Create a compelling story for your game. Introduce the main characters and their motivations in relation to the theme of the CGJ. Describe the setting and key plot points. Explain what the characters are trying to achieve and what obstacles they face.

3. Design

Look & feel, game mechanics, and playability

Describe the game mechanics and design elements. Explain how players interact with the game, the rules, and the objectives. Highlight any unique features or innovations in the game. Clarify whether the game has a clear ending or an open-ended structure. Discuss how players can win or achieve goals in the game.

4. Cultural Material

Integrating cultural material into your game

Explain how the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] has inspired the game. Perhaps a [GIVE EXAMPLES OF THE WAY THE CULTURAL MATERIAL COULD HAVE INSPIRED]. Describe how the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] has influenced the concept, setting, mechanics, and visual style of the game.

FINAL TIPS!

- Be concise & impactful
- Use visuals
- Engage your audience
- Practice, practice, practice!

APPENDIX III: Criteria for Judging Final Games - Example

The following Pitch/Game evaluation criteria, shared with both participants and the jury, clearly outline how the games are judged. These award criteria build on the expectations laid out in the Game Jam Brief and the Pitch Prep instructions, offering an example of how to offer participants a “through line” in their CGJ participation.

Jury Evaluation Criteria

The jury will evaluate all games during the pitches based on the following criteria. Your game can score a maximum of five stars per category. Who will take home the awards?!

1. Theme & Values

How well does your game align with the game jam theme?

- ★ 1 – No clear link to the theme
- ★ 2 – Weakly linked to the theme
- ★ 3 – Moderately linked to the theme
- ★ 4 – Creatively linked to the theme
- ★ 5 – Extremely creative link to the theme

2. Concept

Are the story and characters well thought out and creative?

- ★ 1 – No clear game concept
- ★ 2 – Weak game concept
- ★ 3 – Decent game concept
- ★ 4 – Creative and clear game concept
- ★ 5 – Extremely creative game concept

3. Design

Does the game look good, is it playable, and do the mechanics work well?

- ★ 1 – Poor design + not playable
- ★ 2 – Weak design + playable
- ★ 3 – Decent design + playable
- ★ 4 – Good design + well playable
- ★ 5 – Excellent design + very well playable

4. Cultural Material

Does the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] play a strong role in the game?

- ★ 1 – Not connected to the collection
- ★ 2 – Weak connection to the collection

- ★ 3 – Decent connection to the collection
- ★ 4 – Strong connection to the collection
- ★ 5 – Excellent connection to the collection

APPENDIX IV: CGJ Event Schedule with CGJ Phases - Example

Below is an example from the Aarhus second CGJ, sharing an event schedule for participants that also displays the different CGJ phases.

Program

Saturday 7. September	Sunday 8. September
<p>10.00 – 12.00 Arrival at the ARoS Entrance – we will be there to welcome you! Onboarding (Madkassen, niveau 3) Cultural Game Jam Instructions Art Walk – guided tour</p>	<p>8.00 – 08.45 Welcome to the 2nd day Breakfast/Brunch is served (Madkassen, Niveau 3)</p>
<p>12.00 – 12.30 Lunch is served (Madkassen, Niveau 3)</p>	<p>08.45 – 10:30 IMAGINE PHASE – CONTINUED Jam session with the Coding Pirates and getting ready for the Playtest</p>
<p>12.30-13:30 EXPERIENCE PHASE Start developing your game ideas</p>	<p>10:30-12:00 CREATE PHASE Create your game</p>
<p>13:30-15:30 PLAY PHASE Fair Games will join us in supporting and developing new game ideas Preparation for Expert Council</p>	<p>12.00-12.30 Lunch is served (Madkassen, Niveau 3)</p>
<p>16.00 – 18.00 Expert Council (Salonen, Niveau 3) Each group prepares a short "pitch" of their game idea for a panel of art/game/research/creative experts, and receives feedback towards further development</p>	<p>12.30-15:00 CREATE PHASE Finalise your game for submission and the EXPO</p>
<p>18-19 Dinner is served (Madkassen, niveau 3)</p>	<p>15.00 GAME SUBMISSION on ITCH.io</p>
<p>19-22 IMAGINE PHASE Jam session with the Coding Pirates</p>	<p>15.00-16.30 EXPO (Salonen niveau 3) Each group gets to exhibit their game Networking</p>
	<p>16.30-17 Evaluation and Goodbye :-)</p>

APPENDIX V: CGJ Participant Event Booklet - Example

Below are three examples of participant playbooks. These documents are provided by different QH Cultural Hubs to support participants through the CGJ.

The first example is from the Aarhus Hub second jam. In their approach, this document offers an in-depth understanding of the CGJ phases and the different methods and tools that could be employed. Download the complete playbook [here](#).

The cover page and preface of the Aarhus 2024 CGJ Playbook.

The second example is from the Hilversum Hub's second CGJ in 2024, which is in the process of being planned for a third CGJ in 2025. The Hilversum Hub has titled these "Workbooks" and provided digital and printed copies to participants. These two examples are shared to illustrate the iterative nature of the materials being developed. You will see activity sheets in the second game jam workbook examples, whereas these have been removed and offered individually for the third game jam. You will also see that in the third game jam workbook, there is a connection between the game jam brief, expert council feedback, pitch prep instructions, and jury criteria. Both game jams worked with Dutch-speaking participants, so both workbooks are provided in Dutch.

Download the complete workbook for the Hilversum Hub [CGJ#2 here](#) and [CGJ#3 here](#).

Cover page and contents of the Hilversum Hub 2024 second CGJ Workbook..

The cover page and contents of the Hilversum Hub 2025 third CGJ Workbook.

APPENDIX VI: CGJ Event Organisers' Production Schedule - Example

Learnings from the first and second rounds of CGJs, which have also been incorporated into this practical guide document, are offered below as an example of the Hilversum “Practical Playbook—Master Guide” for their third game jam. Some details in the guide have been redacted, such as phone numbers, links disconnected due to sensitive information, and additional details, such as a roundup of last-minute preparation tasks, removed for clarity.

This example Practical Playbook for the Cultural Game Jam Intervention phase offers an overview of:

- Important Links
- Key Roles
- CGJ Locations Information (addresses, rooms, details, etc.)
- Overview of the Hilversum Hub team, their role in the CGJ and mobile number.
- Production/Time-keeping checklist for Pre-Jam, During Jam, Post-Jam
- List of Additional Facilitators/Experts, their roles and mobile details
- Checklist of still-to-be-completed actions before the CGJ
- The overview schedule per day of the jam details the location, time, programme section, who is involved and their role, materials needed, and any specific actions required at that time.

Download this Practical Playbook example [here](#).